

ROLE OF FATTY ACID β -OXIDATION IN LYMPHANGIOGENESIS

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ABSTRACT

Lymphatic vessels, lined by lymphatic endothelial cells (LECs), are critical for health. A role for metabolism in lymphatic development has not been documented. We report that LEC-specific loss of CPT1a, a rate-controlling step of fatty acid β -oxidation (FAO), impairs lymphatic development. LECs use FAO to proliferate, but also for epigenetic regulation of lymphatic differentiation marker expression. Mechanistically, the transcription factor Prox1 upregulates CPT1a expression, increasing FAO-dependent acetyl-CoA production, which is used by the histone acetyltransferase p300 to acetylate histones at lymphangiogenic genes. Prox1-p300 interaction facilitates preferential histone acetylation at Prox1-target genes. Via this metabolism-dependent mechanism, Prox1 mediates epigenetic changes that promote lymphangiogenesis. Notably, CPT1 blockade inhibits injury-induced lymphangiogenesis, while replenishing acetyl-CoA by supplementing acetate rescues this process *in vivo*.

INTRODUCTION

LECs line lymph vessels that control fluid homeostasis, lipid transport and inflammation. Excess lymphangiogenesis favours metastasis and inflammation^{1,2}, while insufficient lymphangiogenesis causes lymphedema³. In contrast to angiogenesis⁴, it is unknown if metabolic pathways regulate lymphangiogenesis. LECs primarily differentiate from venous endothelial cells (VECs)³. Signals regulating this process include VEGF-C/VEGFR3 signalling and Prox1⁵⁻⁷. Prox1 is critical for the VEC-to-LEC switch *in vivo*, and overexpression of Prox1 in VECs induces differentiation to LECs *in vitro*^{5,8}. Prox1 and VEGFR3 control lymphatic development by inducing LEC differentiation, proliferation and migration^{6,9,10}. Only genetic signals are shown to determine the VEC-to-LEC switch, and a role for metabolism in LEC differentiation has not been considered.

RESULTS

LYMPHATIC ENDOTHELIAL CELLS HAVE HIGH FATTY ACID β -OXIDATION (FAO) FLUX

As nothing is known on LEC metabolism, we compared metabolic rates of LECs to other EC types. FAO was higher in lymphatic than arterial, venous and microvascular ECs, while glycolytic flux was lower (Fig. 1a,b). Analysis of carnitine palmitoyltransferase (CPT) enzymes, rate-controlling steps of FAO, showed that *CPT1A* levels were higher in LECs than venous ECs (VECs) (Fig. 1c,d). Similar to VECs¹¹, *CPT1A* was the most abundantly expressed isoform, however, *CPT1B* and *CPT2* also had higher expression in LECs than VECs, while *CPT1C* was unchanged (Extended Data Fig. 1a). LECs also had higher expression of fatty acid uptake and transport proteins (Extended Data Fig. 1b-f), and higher palmitate uptake (Fig. 1e).

To explore if FAO levels are controlled by lymphangiogenic signals, we overexpressed Prox1 in VECs, an *in vitro* model to induce VEC-to-LEC differentiation⁸. To distinguish *in vitro* Prox1-induced LECs from *in vivo* differentiated LECs, we termed the former “programmed LECs” (pLECs) and the latter LECs. Compared to VECs, Prox1 overexpression to physiological Prox1 levels (not shown) increased CPT1a mRNA and FAO levels in pLECs to levels in LECs (Fig. 1a,c,f,g). In line, Prox1 silencing in LECs (lowering Prox1 mRNA by >85%) reduced CPT1a mRNA levels (Fig. 1h; Extended Data Fig. 1g). During VEC-to-LEC differentiation, VEGFR3 is upregulated, rendering LECs more responsive to the mitogenic/pro-migratory activity of VEGF-C¹². The VEGFR3 ligand VEGF-C elevated FAO (Fig. 1i), while the VEGFR3 inhibitor MAZ51 reduced FAO in LECs but not VECs (Fig. 1j).

CPT1A DELETION IN LECs IMPAIRS LYMPHATIC DEVELOPMENT

The murine lymphatic system develops at embryonic day 9.5 (E9.5) when a subpopulation of VECs in the cardinal vein (CV) express Prox1, initiating LEC differentiation¹³. These Prox1⁺ LEC precursors (initial LECs (iLECs)) migrate dorsally to

form the first lymphatic structures¹³. The formation of the jugular lymphatic sac (JLS) involves VEC-to-LEC differentiation, and the proliferation and migration of mature LECs¹³. To explore if CPT1a plays a role in lymphatic function, we crossed *CPT1a*^{lox/lox} mice¹¹ with mice expressing a tamoxifen-inducible *Prox1-Cre*^{ERT2} in LECs¹⁴ to generate *Prox1-Cre*^{ERT2};*CPT1a*^{lox/lox} mice. Tamoxifen delivery from E8.5-10.5 resulted in gene excision in Cre-positive *Prox1*^{ΔCPT1a} embryos but not Cre-negative wild-type (WT) littermates (*Prox1*). CPT1a deletion was verified by PCR and CPT1a immunoreactivity was undetectable in VEGFR3⁺ LECs in E14.5 *Prox1*^{ΔCPT1a} embryos (Extended Data Fig. 2a-d). We also crossed mice expressing a constitutively active *Prox1*^{FK}-*Cre* that induces recombination in iLECs from E9.5 with *CPT1a*^{lox/lox} mice to generate *Prox1*^{FK}-*Cre*;*CPT1a*^{lox/lox} (*Prox1*^{FK-ΔCPT1a}) embryos, yielding CPT1a gene excision from E9.5 (Extended Data Fig. 2e). Since residual CPT1a protein was still detectable for several days after CPT1a gene inactivation (Supplementary Discussion 1; Extended Data Fig. 2f-n), we focused on lymphatic development from E15.5 onwards, when residual CPT1a protein levels were no longer detectable (Extended Data Fig. 2o,p). There were no major defects in the heart, arteries or veins, and only minor abnormalities in the liver of mutant embryos (not shown).

Macroscopic inspection revealed edema (Fig. 2a; Extended Data Fig. 3a) and variable presence of bleeding spots with TER119⁺ erythroid precursors at E14.5 and blood within lymphatic structures at E16.5, a mark of dysfunctional lymphatics due to incomplete separation of lymphatic from venous vessels¹⁵, in a large fraction of mutant embryos (Extended Data Fig. 3b-d). Analysis of dermal lymphatic vessels in WT embryos at E15.5-16.5 revealed a branched plexus, where continuous tubular lymphatic vessels with smooth contours and largely uniform size grew to the midline (Fig. 2b; Extended Data Fig. 3e). In contrast, lymphatics in mutant embryos exhibited severe impairment of network outgrowth to the midline, and formed a disorganized lacy mesh with fewer branches (Fig. 2b-e; Extended Data Fig. 3e-h). Overall, lymphatics were wider in mutant embryos, even though some were thinner (Fig. 2f; Extended Data Fig. 3i). In the most severely affected embryos, isolated ball-like structures of LECs (“lymphatic islands”¹⁶)

were detected (Extended Data Fig. 3j). Delivery of tamoxifen to $\text{Prox1}^{\Delta\text{CPT1a}}$ embryos between E10.5-E12.5, to delete CPT1a in LECs after the JLS formation has initiated, also impaired dermal lymphatic formation (Extended Data Fig. 3k-m).

The dysmorphic features and reduced lymphatic outgrowth in mutant embryos was due to branching defects as a result of impeded LEC migration¹⁷, aggravated by impaired LEC proliferation and differentiation (resulting from reduced VEGFR3 and Prox1 levels). Indeed, we observed reduced numbers of filopodia (Fig. 2g,h; Extended Data Fig. 3n,o) and proliferating BrdU^+ LECs (Fig. 2i), and lower VEGFR3 immunoreactivity in sprouts at the lymphatic front in $\text{Prox1}^{\Delta\text{CPT1a}}$ embryos (Extended Data Fig. 3n,p). CPT1a loss also impaired lymphatic development in the trachea (Extended Data Fig. 4a-c). Abnormal lymphatic development and edema were present in ~70% of mutant embryos. Overall, CPT1a in LECs regulates lymphatic development. Qualitatively similar results were obtained when intercrossing $\text{CPT1a}^{\text{lox/lox}}$ mice with a $\text{Flt4-Cre}^{\text{ERT2}}$ inducible driver¹⁸ (Extended Data Fig. 4d-i).

PHARMACOLOGICAL INHIBITION OF CPT1 IMPAIRS LYMPHATIC DEVELOPMENT

To achieve rapid inhibition of FAO at earlier stages, we treated pregnant mice with the pharmacological CPT1 blocker etomoxir (using a dose that did not affect embryonic blood vessels), from E8.5-10.5 during the period of LEC differentiation and initial lymphatic formation. Analysis at E10.5 revealed that etomoxir reduced the number of $\text{Prox1}^+/\text{VEGFR3}^+$ iLECs within and emigrating from the cardinal vein (Fig. 2j-l). This reduction in iLECs impaired JLS formation at E12.5 (Fig. 2m-o), and induced subdermal edema at E14.5, occasionally with bleeding spots (not shown), with a reduced area of the JLS and peripheral lymphatic vessels at E14.5 (Extended Data Fig. 4j-l). Analysis of etomoxir-treated embryos at E16.5 confirmed this lymphatic defect, with abnormal formation of dermal lymphatic vessels, with fewer filopodia and proliferating LECs, illustrating that FAO is necessary for LEC migration and proliferation *in vivo* (Extended Data Fig. 4m-s). Etomoxir (at this dose) did not prominently affect embryonic

development, causing only minimal morphological changes in the heart. Apart from some vascular defects (bleeding), we did not observe changes in blood vessel size (Extended Data Fig. 4t). Prolonged treatment with etomoxir (from E8.5-14.5) yielded a similar phenotype, with more severe defects in dorsal lymphatic vessel branching and width (Extended Data Fig. 4u-x).

FAO REGULATES PROLIFERATION, MIGRATION AND DIFFERENTIATION OF LECs

We determined the cellular mechanisms whereby CPT1a-driven FAO regulates lymphangiogenesis. CPT1a knockdown (CPT1a^{KD}) in LECs, lowering CPT1a protein levels and FAO (Extended Data Fig. 5a,b), reduced LEC proliferation and migration, and vessel sprouting (Fig. 3a-c; Extended Data Fig. 5c-e), without compromising LEC survival (Extended Data Fig. 5f). Impaired LEC proliferation and migration can contribute to the lymphatic defects in the absence of CPT1a in LECs *in vivo*.

Since (i) VEC-to-LEC differentiation regulates lymphatic development^{10,19,20}; (ii) fewer iLECs were detected in etomoxir-treated embryos; and (iii) impaired LEC differentiation can impede lymphatic formation (e.g. low VEGFR3 levels can reduce responses to VEGF-C), we explored a possible role for CPT1a in LEC differentiation. CPT1a^{KD} returned the elevated FAO in pLECs to basal levels in VECs (Extended Data Fig. 5g). CPT1a^{KD} preceding Prox1 overexpression impaired pLEC differentiation, as evidenced by reduced levels of VEGFR3 (Fig. 3d,e) and LEC-enriched markers (Extended Data Fig. 5h,i). This impaired LEC differentiation by CPT1a^{KD} was not due to a reduction of Prox1 levels in pLECs (Extended Data Fig. 5j). Etomoxir phenocopied the effects of CPT1a^{KD} in pLECs (Extended Data Fig. 5k) (for additional characterization of FAO's role in VEC-to-LEC differentiation, see Supplementary Discussion 2; Extended Data Fig. 5l-v). LECs from embryos lacking CPT1a also visually had reduced VEGFR3 immunoreactivity (Extended Data Fig. 3n,p).

FAO: A ROLE IN EPIGENETIC MODIFICATION?

CPT1a^{KD} did not cause energy distress (Extended Data Fig. 6a) or redox imbalance (Supplementary Discussion 3; Extended Data Fig. 6b-e). Instead, fatty acids provided acetyl-coenzyme A (acetyl-CoA), which helped to sustain the TCA cycle and dNTP synthesis for proliferation of LECs in conjunction with an anaplerotic substrate, as in VECs¹¹ (Supplementary Discussion 3; Extended Data Fig. 6f-k). However, since the regulation of dNTP synthesis unlikely explained FAO's effects on LEC differentiation and migration, we explored if FAO regulated lymphatic formation via other mechanisms. We hypothesized that acetyl-CoA generated by FAO in LECs might be involved in epigenetic modification of lymphangiogenic gene expression. We focused on a regulation of VEGFR3 expression by FAO since: (i) VEGFR3 transcription is regulated by histone acetyltransferase (HAT) p300²¹; (ii) LEC differentiation by Prox1 induces VEGFR3 expression, thereby enhancing LEC responses to VEGF-C; (iii) VEGFR3 is required for proliferation and migration of LECs²²; and (iv) CPT1a-deficient LECs *in vivo* had lower VEGFR3 protein levels (see above), suggesting that CPT1a-driven FAO regulates VEGFR3 levels. Hence, we hypothesized that FAO also regulated lymphatic vessel formation via epigenetic regulation of VEGFR3 transcription.

PROX1 INDUCES FAO VIA UPREGULATION OF CPT1A TRANSCRIPTION AND INTERACTS WITH P300

In contrast to wild type Prox1, overexpression of a mutant Prox1 lacking DNA-binding domains⁸ was unable to induce CPT1a expression (Extended Data Fig. 7a) or increase FAO (Fig. 3f), implying that the DNA-binding ability of Prox1 is required. Unbiased whole genome analysis using chromatin immunoprecipitation sequencing (ChIP-seq) using an anti-FLAG antibody in VECs expressing FLAG-tagged Prox1 (Prox1-FLAG) revealed the presence of two Prox1 binding sites, one at the promoter (A) and one in the intergenic region (B) of the CPT1a gene (Fig. 3g). These binding sites were confirmed in pLECs by

ChIP-seq using an anti-Prox1 antibody (Extended Data Fig. 7b), and by Prox1-ChIP followed by PCR (Extended Data Fig. 7c). Cloning of CPT1a fragments in luciferase reporter constructs confirmed that Prox1 overexpression enhanced CPT1a gene transcription (Fig. 3h). Thus, Prox1 upregulates FAO, partly via induction of CPT1a gene expression. Co-immunoprecipitation showed that Prox1 interacts with p300 in pLECs (Fig. 3i). Whole genome p300 ChIP-seq showed that p300 was enriched at 76% of Prox1 peaks (Fig. 3j, lanes 1-5). Blockade of p300 using SGC-CBP30²³ prior to Prox1 overexpression phenocopied the effect of CPT1a^{KD} and prevented Prox1-induced expression of VEGFR3 and LEC-enriched markers (Extended Data Fig. 7d-f). Silencing p300 confirmed these findings (Extended Data Fig. 7g-j).

FAO-DERIVED ACETYL-COA PRODUCTION SUPPORTS VEGFR3 EXPRESSION

Acetyl-CoA/CoA ratios are a determinant of histone acetylation by p300²⁴, and the ratio of acetyl-CoA/CoA was increased upon Prox1 overexpression, while CPT1a^{KD} reduced the ratio to baseline (Fig. 4a). Cytosolic acetyl-CoA is generated after mitochondrial export of the TCA cycle metabolite citrate to the cytosol by citrate transporter SLC25A1, where it is converted to acetyl-CoA by ATP citrate lyase (ACLY). Pharmacological inhibition of SLC25A1 using 1,2,3-benzenetricarboxylate (BTC) or ACLY silencing in pLECs prevented Prox1-induced VEGFR3 expression, phenocopying CPT1a^{KD} (Fig. 4b,c; Supplementary Discussion 4; Extended Data Fig. 7k-s). Thus, FAO-derived acetyl-CoA supports Prox1-induced VEGFR3 expression.

FAO CO-REGULATES VEGFR3 EXPRESSION VIA P300-MEDIATED HISTONE ACETYLATION

Acetylation of histone H3 at lysine 9 (H3K9ac) by p300 is sensitive to acetyl-CoA levels²⁵. Moreover, H3K9ac is an important mark of active gene promoters²⁶. Prox1 overexpression in pLECs increased H3K9ac levels, while CPT1a^{KD} reduced H3K9ac levels in pLECs to levels in VECs (Fig. 4d). Fatty acid-derived carbons contributed to histone acetylation, as incubation with [U-¹⁴C]-palmitate revealed increased incorporation in the

nuclear histone fraction in pLECs, and this incorporation was reduced by CPT1a^{KD} (Fig. 4e). Furthermore, whole genome H3K9ac ChIP-seq revealed that nearly all (94%) sites of Prox1 and p300 co-enrichment were marked by H3K9ac, suggesting the functionality of p300 as a HAT at these sites (Fig. 3j, lanes 1-6; Supplementary Table 1).

PROX1 AND FAO CO-REGULATE HISTONE H3K9 ACETYLATION AT LYMPHATIC GENES

Whole genome analysis of H3K9ac ChIP-seq in VECs and pLECs identified 2,053 H3K9ac peaks with increased histone acetylation as a result of Prox1 overexpression (Fig. 4f; Supplementary Table 2). Unbiased analyses revealed that lymphatic genesets²⁷ had greater enrichment of H3K9ac after Prox1 overexpression than vascular genesets, non-Prox1-target genes or genesets of unrelated processes (Fig. 4g; Extended Data Fig. 8a,b). Compared to VECs, increased H3K9ac in pLECs was observed at key lymphangiogenic genes, including VEGFR3 (Fig. 5a; Extended Data Fig. 8c,e). Importantly, the regions of enhanced H3K9 acetylation at these LEC genes had at least one Prox1 binding site in close proximity. Further, CPT1a^{KD} in pLECs reduced H3K9ac at these sites (Fig. 5a; Extended Data Fig. 8c,e). Differential H3K9ac at VEGFR3, Prox1 and Sox18 was confirmed by H3K9ac ChIP and quantitative PCR (Fig. 5b; Extended Data Fig. 8d,f). In congruence, there was increased p300 enrichment at the Prox1 binding site in the VEGFR3 gene (Extended Data Fig. 8g,h). Conversely, VEC genes such as VEGFR2 lacked Prox1 binding sites (Extended Data Fig. 8i), and correspondingly did not show changes in H3K9ac in pLECs versus VECs (Extended Data Fig. 8j). Of note, the CPT1A gene, which has two Prox1 binding sites, showed increased p300 binding (Extended Data Fig. 9a-c) and H3K9ac at the Prox1 binding sites upon Prox1 overexpression (Extended Data Fig. 9d,e). In line, p300 inhibition by SGC- CBP30 decreased CPT1A mRNA levels and FAO (Fig. 5c,d). CPT1a^{KD} did not reduce Prox1 or p300 interaction with the CPT1A or VEGFR3 promoters, supporting a role for FAO in providing acetyl-CoA for histone acetylation (Extended Data Fig. 9b,c,f-i).

INHIBITION OF FAO REDUCES PATHOLOGICAL LYMPHANGIOGENESIS

In a corneal model of injury-induced lymphangiogenesis²⁸, LYVE1⁺/CD31⁺ lymphatic vessels and CD31⁺ blood vessels sprout into the avascular cornea (Fig. 5e,f; Extended Data Fig. 10a,b). Treatment with etomoxir impaired lymphangiogenesis (Fig. 5f; Extended Data Fig. 10a,b). This was partly due to effects on LEC migration (as suggested by reduced branch points of LYVE1⁺/CD31⁺ lymphatic vessels (Fig. 5g)). Also, corneal vessels in etomoxir-treated animals had reduced VEGFR3 and H3K9ac immunoreactivity (Fig. 5h-k). In line with previous observations¹¹, growth of CD31⁺ blood vessels was impaired by etomoxir (Extended Data Fig. 10c-g).

ACETATE SUPPLEMENTS RESCUE LYMPHATIC DEFECTS UPON FAO INHIBITION

We hypothesized that supplementation with acetate, which can be converted to acetyl-CoA²⁹, could replenish acetyl-CoA pools and recover the pLEC differentiation and sprouting defect caused by CPT1a^{KD}. Indeed, supplementation with acetate upon CPT1a^{KD} rescued the acetyl-CoA/CoA ratio (Fig. 6a), H3K9ac levels (Fig. 6b) and VEGFR3 expression (Fig. 6c). Also, acetate supplementation recovered H3K9ac at the *VEGFR3* gene (Fig. 6d) and rescued pLEC spheroid sprouting upon CPT1a^{KD} (Fig. 6e). Injection of acetate, elevating plasma acetate levels (Extended Data Fig. 10h), restored lymphangiogenesis to levels observed in vehicle-treated controls in the corneal assay (Fig. 6f-h; Extended Data Fig. 10i,j). In line, VEGFR3 and H3K9ac immunoreactivity were restored to levels in vehicle-treated mice after corneal injury (Fig. 6i,j). Since sprouting of new lymphatics originates from pre-established differentiated LECs, acetate likely rescued LEC proliferation and migration in this model.

DISCUSSION

Our data show that FAO promotes proliferation of LECs via the same mechanism that controls VEC proliferation, i.e. fatty acids provide acetyl-CoA, which helps to sustain the TCA cycle and dNTP synthesis in conjunction with an anaplerotic substrate¹¹. However, our most intriguing finding is that FAO also regulates LEC differentiation via epigenetic control of key lymphatic genes. This is not only important for VEC-to-LEC differentiation during initial lymphatic development, but can also determine the responsiveness of LECs to lymphangiogenic factors during lymphatic sprouting.

Our findings extend the current knowledge of how Prox1 orchestrates lymphatic development. In the traditional model, Prox1 acts as a transcription factor that binds to the promoter region of lymphatic genes and induces their transcription^{6,8}, a mechanism that still remains valid. However, in the adapted model (based on our findings), we propose that Prox1 in addition bolsters its own transcriptional activity via a dual mechanism (Extended Data Fig. 10k): (i) first, via induction of CPT1a expression, Prox1 enhances the production of FAO-derived acetyl-CoA, used by p300 for histone acetylation at lymphatic genes, an epigenetic process that enhances access of Prox1 to these sites by converting condensed chromatin into a more relaxed structure; and (ii) second, by interacting with p300, Prox1 preferentially recruits this HAT to Prox1-target genes, thereby increasing selectivity. Combined, Prox1 ensures more selective and effective expression of lymphatic genes by integrating metabolism with transcription.

Pharmacological blockade of CPT1 inhibits injury-induced lymphangiogenesis, which may hint at an underappreciated therapeutic potential of lowering FAO for inhibition of pathological lymphangiogenesis, such as in cancer, in which excessive lymphatic growth promotes metastasis³⁰. Our findings that acetate supplementation rescues the postnatal lymphangiogenesis defects upon FAO inhibition show the dynamic nature of the regulation of lymphatic sprouting by metabolites. It will be interesting to explore if dietary modulation of fatty acids or supplementation with metabolites

(acetate) can be utilized to promote lymphangiogenesis in pathological conditions such as lymphedema.

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END NOTES

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS: We thank R. Adams and T. Mäkinen for providing the *VE-cadherin(PAC)-Cre^{ERT2}* and *Prox1-Cre^{ERT2}* mice, respectively. This work was supported by: fellowships from FWO (BWW, XW, BT, JK, RM, UB, JG, BG), Marie Curie (BWW, MG, UB), EMBO (HH) and LE&RN/FDRS (AZ); and supporting grants, PC: IUAP P7/03, Methusalem funding by the Flemish Government, FWO G.0598.12, G.0532.10, G.0817.11, G.0834.13, 1.5.202.10.N Krediet aan navorsers, Leducq Transatlantic Network Artemis, AXA Research Fund (1465), Foundation against Cancer, ERC Advanced Research Grant (EU-ERC269073, PC), ERC Starting Grant (IMAGINED-201293, AL) and German Research Foundation (DFG) Grants (CRC629, CRC656, FK).

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS: BWW, AZ, XW, BT, IC, JK, MG, RM, HH, UB, SB, SV, JG, HZ, CD, CS, RH, VM, SW, ML, BG, LS, MD, GE performed research and/or analyzed the data; BWW, AZ, XW, BT, IC, MD, DL, PC designed experiments; MK, SJ, FK, SMF provided mice and/or advice; AL, AN, LM, DL provided reagents and discussed results; BWW, AZ made the figures; BWW, PC wrote the paper; PC conceptualized the study. All authors discussed the results and commented on the manuscript.

AUTHOR INFORMATION: Reprints and permissions information is available at www.nature.com/reprints. PC declares to be named as inventor on patent applications, claiming subject matter related to the results described in this paper. The other authors declare no competing financial interests. Correspondence and requests for materials should be addressed to PC (peter.carmeliet@vib-kuleuven.be).

LEGENDS TO THE FIGURES

FIGURE 1: CPT1A EXPRESSION AND FAO FLUX ARE HIGHER IN LECs

a,b, Metabolic fluxes in human umbilical vein ECs (HUVEC), human umbilical artery ECs (HUAEC), human dermal microvascular blood ECs (HDBEC), human dermal microvascular lymphatic ECs (HDLEC) and human pulmonary lymphatic ECs (HPLEC). **a**, FAO flux. **b**, Glycolytic flux. **c-e**, Comparison of LECs *versus* venous ECs (VECs). **c**, *CPT1A* mRNA expression. **d**, Immunoblot for CPT1a (quantitation of CPT1a/ β -actin densitometry beneath blots). **e**, Palmitate uptake. **f,g**, Comparison of Prox1-overexpression in VECs (programmed LECs, pLECs) *versus* VECs. **f**, *CPT1A* mRNA expression. **g**, FAO flux. **h**, *CPT1A* mRNA expression in LECs without (ctrl) and with siRNA-mediated silencing of Prox1 (siProx1). **i,j**, FAO flux in LECs or VECs upon treatment. **i**, Treatment with vehicle (ctrl) or VEGF-C. **j**, Treatment with vehicle (ctrl) or MAZ51. Mean \pm s.e.m.; n = 3 for a-g,i,j. n = 7 for h. * $p < 0.05$, NS = not statistically significant by ANOVA and Bonferroni post-hoc test (a,b,i,j) or *t*-test (c-h).

FIGURE 2: INHIBITION OF CPT1A IMPAIRS LYMPHATIC DEVELOPMENT

a-h, Embryonic phenotype of WT (Prox1^{FK}) and $\text{Prox1}^{\text{FK}\Delta\text{CPT1a}}$ embryos. **a**, Stereomicrographs at E14.5. Asterisks: subdermal edema. **b**, LYVE1⁺ dermal lymphatic network in E16.5 embryos. White dashed lines: left/right lymphatic fronts. Lower panels: high magnifications of red boxed regions. Scale bars: 500 μm . **c-f**, Lymphatic vessel outgrowth (c), total length (d), branch points (e), and width (f). **g**, LYVE1⁺ (white) dermal lymphatic sprouts at the growing front. Arrows: filopodia. Scale bars: 10 μm . **h**, Number of filopodia per sprout. **i**, BrdU⁺ LECs in dermal lymphatics in E15.5 Prox1 and $\text{Prox1}^{\Delta\text{CPT1a}}$ embryos. **j-o**, Embryonic phenotype of vehicle- (ctrl) or etomoxir-treated (eto) embryos. **j**, Immunostaining for Prox1 (red) and VEGFR3 (green) from the jugular region of E10.5 embryos. Insets: single channel Prox1 signal of white boxed regions. Solid white line: dorsal aorta (DA); dashed white line: cardinal vein (CV); arrows: migrating Prox1⁺/VEGFR3⁺ LEC precursors. Scale bars: 50 μm . **k,l**, Prox1⁺/VEGFR3⁺ cells within and emigrating from the CV in E10.5 embryos. **m**, VEGFR3 immunostaining in jugular region of E12.5 embryos. Solid white line: jugular vein (JV); dashed white line: jugular lymphatic sac (JLS). Scale bars: 100 μm . **n,o**, JV and JLS area in E12.5 embryos. Mean \pm s.e.m.; (n = 9 embryos for Prox1^{FK} ; n = 5 embryos for $\text{Prox1}^{\text{FK}\Delta\text{CPT1a}}$; 3 litters for c-f,h); (n = 3 embryos for WT; n = 6 embryos for $\text{Prox1}^{\Delta\text{CPT1a}}$; 1 litter for i); (n = 6 embryos for ctrl; n = 5 embryos for eto; 2 litters per group for k,l); (n = 15 embryos for ctrl; n = 18 embryos for eto; 2 litters each group for n,o). * $p < 0.05$, NS = not statistically significant by *t*-test.

FIGURE 3: CPT1A REGULATES VEC-TO-LEC DIFFERENTIATION

a-c, Comparison of LECs without (ctrl) and with CPT1a^{KD}. **a**, [³H]-thymidine incorporation into DNA. **b**, Scratch wound migration assay. **c**, Total sprout length in LEC spheroids. **d,e**, Comparison of pLECs without (ctrl) and with CPT1a^{KD} versus VECs. **d**, *VEGFR3* mRNA expression. **e**, Immunoblots for *VEGFR3* and *CPT1a* (quantitation of *VEGFR3*/β-actin densitometry beneath blots, normalized to the densitometric ratio for VECs). **f**, FAO in VECs expressing wild-type *Prox1* (*Prox1*) or a *Prox1*-DNA-binding mutant (*Prox1mut*) versus control VECs. **g**, *Prox1*-FLAG enrichment around the human *CPT1A* gene (green), compared to empty-FLAG control (blue) and input (black), determined by ChIP-seq analysis of VECs expressing FLAG-tagged *Prox1* (*Prox1*-FLAG) or empty-FLAG. Reads are binned in 100 bp intervals, and expressed per million reads (y axis). Averages of 2 ChIP-seq experiments. Top line: gene scheme; grey blocks: *CPT1A* exons; black blocks: exons of adjacent genes; red arrowheads: statistically significant peaks of *Prox1* enrichment ($q < 0.1$). Bottom line: chromosomal location (hg19). **h**, Luciferase reporter activity from “A” and “B” from panel g for the *CPT1A* gene in VECs and pLECs. **i**, Immunoblot for *Prox1*-FLAG (top) and p300 (bottom) upon co-immunoprecipitation (IP) for p300 in *Prox1*-FLAG expressing VECs. Lane 1: input sample; Lane 2: empty; Lane 3: isotype IgG-IP; Lane 4: p300-IP. **j**, Read density heatmaps (in colour scales) showing the intensity of *Prox1*-FLAG (red, lane 1), *Prox1* (*Prox1*; red, lane 2), p300 (green, lane 3) and H3K9ac (blue, lane 6) ChIP-seq signal in pLECs versus empty-FLAG (FLAG immunoprecipitation in control VECs, lane 4) or input ($n = 2$, lane 5). Regions are plotted, centered on the *Prox1*-FLAG peak summits as determined using MACS software, with regions ranked by the corresponding strength of the p300 and H3K9ac ChIP-seq signals. Each of the 5,611 rows represents a region of 10 kb, split in 100 bp bins that are shaded according to the number of ChIP-seq reads mapped to that bin, as indicated by the colour scales. Mean ± s.e.m.; $n = 3$ independent experiments for a-f,h. Statistical analysis for ChIP-seq described in Methods. * $p < 0.05$, NS = not statistically significant by *t*-test (a-c,h) or ANOVA and Bonferroni post-hoc test (d,e,f).

FIGURE 4: PROX1-MEDIATED FAO PRODUCES ACETYL-COA FOR HISTONE H3 ACETYLATION

a, Acetyl-CoA/CoA ratios in pLECs at baseline (ctrl) and upon CPT1a^{KD} *versus* VECs. **b**, *VEGFR3* mRNA expression in pLECs with and without inhibition of SLC25A1 by BTC *versus* VECs. **c**, *VEGFR3* mRNA expression in pLECs without (ctrl) and with silencing of ACLY (ACLY^{KD}) *versus* VECs. **d**, Immunoblot of acetylated lysine 9 (H3K9ac) and total histone H3 in ctrl and CPT1a^{KD} pLECs *versus* VECs (quantitation of H3K9ac relative to total histone H3 beneath blots, normalized to the densitometric ratio for VECs). **e**, [¹⁴C]-palmitate carbon incorporation in acidic histone fraction in ctrl and CPT1a^{KD} pLECs *versus* VECs. **f**, Plot of H3K9ac reads per million at 41,241 H3K9ac peaks in pLECs *versus* VECs. Y-axis represents log₂-transformed difference in H3K9ac levels between VECs and pLECs; X-axis represents log₂-transformed average number of reads at H3K9ac sites per million of reads across all experiments. Significantly increased (red) and decreased (green) levels of acetylation upon Prox1 overexpression were determined using EdgeR (exact tests, FDR = 5%) and 3 independent biological replicates. **g**, Proportion of LEC (7/17 genes, 41.2%) *versus* blood endothelial cell (BEC) (3/35 genes, 8.5%) genes with enhanced H3K9ac levels (red portion) in pLECs *versus* VECs. Mean ± s.e.m.; n = 3 independent experiments for a-e. Statistical analysis for ChIP-seq is described in Methods. *p<0.05 by ANOVA and Bonferroni post-hoc test (a-e) and Chi-square test (g).

FIGURE 5: FAO ENHANCES HISTONE ACETYLATION AT LYMPHATIC GENES

a,b, Experiments involving pLECs without (ctrl) and with CPT1a^{KD} *versus* VECs. **a**, H3K9ac enrichment around the *VEGFR3* gene. Grey boxes at chromosomal locations: regions with H3K9ac peak areas; green top half of box: regions of significantly enhanced H3K9ac in pLECs *versus* VECs; red bottom half of box: regions of significantly reduced H3K9ac in CPT1a^{KD} pLECs *versus* control pLECs. q-value is the FDR corrected p-value. Asterisk denotes region confirmed by qPCR in panel b. **b**, Quantitative PCR verification on H3K9ac ChIP samples, relative to input. **c,d**, Comparison of pLECs treated with vehicle (ctrl) or p300 inhibitor SGC-CBP30 (SGC) *versus* VECs. **c**, *CPT1A* mRNA expression. **d**, FAO flux. **e-k**, Corneal cauterization-induced injury in mice treated with vehicle (ctrl) or etomoxir (eto). **e**, LYVE1⁺ (green) lymphatic vessel outgrowth in ctrl- or eto-treated mice. CD31 immunostaining (red) highlights blood vessels, and also weakly stains lymphatic vessels. Scale bars: 750 μ m. **f,g**, Lymphatic vessel outgrowth area and branch point density. **h,i**, VEGFR3 immunostaining of lymphatic sprouts and quantitation of VEGFR3 immunoreactivity. Scale bars: 10 μ m. **j,k**, H3K9ac immunostaining of lymphatic sprouts and quantitation of H3K9ac fluorescence. Scale bars: 10 μ m. Mean \pm s.e.m.; n = 3 independent experiments for b-d; n = 5 mice per group for f,g,i,k. Statistical analysis for ChIP-seq is described in Methods. *p<0.05 by ANOVA and Bonferroni post-hoc test (b-d) or t-test (f,g,i,k).

FIGURE 6: ACETATE SUPPLEMENTATION RECOVERS LYMPHANGIOGENESIS

a-d, Experiments involving pLECs at baseline (ctrl) and upon CPT1a^{KD}, with and without acetate supplementation. **a**, Acetyl-CoA/CoA ratios, relative to ctrl. **b**, Immunoblots for H3K9ac and total histone H3 (quantitation of H3K9ac/total histone H3 densitometry beneath blots, normalized to the densitometric ratio for ctrl pLECs). **c**, Immunoblot for VEGFR3 (quantitation of VEGFR3/ β -actin densitometry beneath blots). **d**, Quantitative PCR for the sequence of *VEGFR3* (asterisk in Fig. 5a) on H3K9ac ChIP samples, expressed relative to input. **e**, Total sprout length from spheroid sprouting assay in CPT1a^{KD} pLECs without and with acetate (+ac) *versus* pLECs without CPT1a^{KD} (ctrl). **f-j**, Corneal cauterization-induced injury in WT mice treated with vehicle (ctrl), acetate only (ac), etomoxir only (eto), or etomoxir + acetate (eto+ac). **f**, LYVE1⁺ lymphatic outgrowth (green). CD31 immunostaining (red) highlights blood vessels, and also weakly stains lymphatic vessels. Scale bars: 500 μ m. **g,h**, Lymphatic vessel outgrowth area and branch point density. **i,j**, Quantitation of VEGFR3 immunoreactivity and average H3K9ac fluorescence per nucleus in lymphatic sprouts. Mean \pm s.e.m.; n = 3 independent experiments for a-e; n = 10 mice per group for g,h; n = 6 mice per group for i,j. *p<0.05; NS = not statistically significant, by ANOVA and Bonferroni post-hoc test.

METHODS

MOUSE STRAINS: (i) $CPT1a^{lox/lox}$ mice were produced as previously described¹¹. (ii) $Prox1-Cre^{ERT2}$ mice (generously provided by T. Mäkinen³¹) were intercrossed with $CPT1a^{lox/lox}$ mice and termed $Prox1-Cre^{ERT2}:CPT1a^{lox/lox}$ mice. For experiments involving embryos, 50 mg kg⁻¹ tamoxifen was administered to the pregnant dams daily by oral gavage between embryonic days (E) 8.5-10.5 or E10.5-12.5 of the pregnancy stage for experiments investigating the phenotype of later stage gene excision. Successful Cre-mediated excision of the floxed *Cpt1a* segment in tamoxifen-treated mice (termed $Prox1^{\Delta CPT1a}$ mice) was confirmed via PCR analysis of genomic DNA using primers spanning the floxed region, by the appearance of a 300-bp band. (iii) $VE-cadherin(PAC)-Cre^{ERT2}$ mice (generously provided by R. Adams) were intercrossed with $CPT1a^{lox/lox}$ mice, termed $VE-cadherin(PAC)-Cre^{ERT2}:CPT1a^{lox/lox}$ mice. (iv) $Flt4-Cre^{ERT2}$ mice (generously provided by S. Ortega¹⁸) were intercrossed with $CPT1a^{lox/lox}$ mice, and termed $Flt4-Cre^{ERT2}:CPT1a^{lox/lox}$ mice. (v) Mice constitutively expressing Cre under the transcriptional regulation of the murine *Prox1* promoter were generated previously by F. Kiefer, and termed $Prox1^{FK}-Cre$ mice. Briefly, in a BAC clone (RP23-190F21) carrying a ~239 kb sized genomic fragment of the murine chromosome 1 encoding murine *Prox1*, the second exon of the *Prox1* gene was replaced by an in-frame insertion of a sequence encoding a nuclear localization signal (NLS), the Cre cDNA and the SV40 polyA. The resulting *Prox1-Cre-pA* BAC clone was then used for zygote injection to generate transgenic mice. Details on the BAC design and on the characterization of the transgenic mice will be published elsewhere (F. Kiefer; manuscript in preparation). $Prox1^{FK}-Cre$ mice were intercrossed with $CPT1a^{lox/lox}$ mice. Tamoxifen treatment of Cre^{ERT2} driver lines, and verification of Cre-mediated excision of the floxed *Cpt1a* segment in all Cre lines, was done as described above. WT *C57Bl/6* mice (obtained from the KU Leuven Animal Facility or purchased from Charles River) were used for generation of etomoxir-treated embryos and for the corneal cauterization experiments. Intraperitoneal injections of 30 mg kg⁻¹ etomoxir were given daily after cauterization. For mouse experiments, all image quantifications (see below) were performed by researchers blinded to the group

allocation. All procedures involving animals and their care were approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Research Advisory Committee of the KU Leuven) and were performed in accordance with the institutional and national guidelines and regulations.

CHEMICALS AND REAGENTS: 1,2,3-benzenetricarboxylic acid hydrate (BTC), L-carnitine sodium salt, dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), dNTP mix, endothelial cell growth supplements (ECGS), Evans blue, heparin, MAZ51, mitomycin C (MitoC), polybrene, sodium acetate, sodium butyrate and trichostatin A were from Sigma-Aldrich (Bornem, Belgium). SGC-CBP30 was from Tocris (Bristol, UK). L-glutamine and penicillin-streptomycin were from GIBCO (Invitrogen, Life Technologies, Ghent Belgium). Dithiothreitol (DTT) was from Pierce (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Aalst, Belgium). Collagen type 1 (rat tail) was from Millipore (Merck Millipore, Overijse, Belgium). Recombinant human VEGF-C was from Peprotech EC Ltd. (London, UK). The CPT1a inhibitor (+)-etomoxir sodium salt hydrate was purchased either from Sigma-Aldrich, CNIO Carlos III Therapies, WuXi AppTec Co., Ltd, or H.P.O. Wolf. [9,10-³H]-palmitic acid, [5-³H]-D-glucose, [³H]-thymidine and [U-¹⁴C]-palmitic acid, were from Perkin Elmer (Zaventem, Belgium). [U-¹³C]-palmitate was purchased from Cambridge Isotope Laboratories (Tewksbury, MA, USA).

CELL CULTURE: Human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs) and human umbilical artery endothelial cells (HUAECs) were freshly isolated from multiple donors as previously described ³² (with approval from the Medical Ethical Committee KU Leuven / UZ Leuven and informed consent obtained from all subjects), were regularly tested for mycoplasma and were used between passages 1 and 5. HUVECs were initially cultured in M199 medium (1 mg mL⁻¹ D-glucose) supplemented with 20% fetal bovine serum (FBS; Biochrom GmbH, Germany), 2 mM L-glutamine, 30 µg L⁻¹ ECGS, 10 units mL⁻¹ heparin, 50 IU mL⁻¹ penicillin and 50 µg mL⁻¹ streptomycin, and switched to growth in endothelial cell growth medium 2 (ECGM2, Promocell, Heidelberg, Germany) for all experiments. In all experiments, HUVECs were always used as single-donor cultures. Human dermal lymphatic endothelial cells (HDLECs), human pulmonary lymphatic endothelial cells

(HPLEC) and human dermal blood endothelial cells (HDBECs) were either freshly isolated from multiple donors as previously described³³ or commercially purchased from Promocell and used between passages 3 and 8. 293T cells were cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM; Invitrogen) supplemented with 10% (v/v) fetal bovine serum, 2 mM L-glutamine, 100 U mL⁻¹ penicillin, 110 mg L⁻¹ sodium pyruvate and 100 µg mL⁻¹ streptomycin. Cells were maintained in 5% CO₂ and 95% air at 37 °C.

LENTIVIRAL TRANSDUCTIONS: Lentiviral expression vector constructs for prospero homeobox protein 1 (Prox1) and GFP control virus were obtained from GeneCopoeia (Rockville, USA) and cloned in the pRRLsinPPT.CMV.MCS.MM W prevector³⁴. FLAG-tagged Prox1 was also obtained from GeneCopoeia and cloned into the pRRL prevector, and an empty vector pRRL virus was used as control. To generate lentiviral expression vector for human CPT1a, the cDNA ORF clone inserted into a pLenti-C-mGFP vector was purchased from Origene (Origene USA, Rockville, MD, USA). To generate shRNA vectors against CPT1a, ACLY, p300 or VLCAD, oligonucleotides encoding the respective shRNA were cloned into the pLKO.1 vector (Sigma; oligonucleotide sequences are available upon request). For CPT1a, 2 non-overlapping shRNAs (KD1, KD2) were used; CPT1a^{KD} in the manuscript and figures refers to KD1 unless otherwise listed. A nonsense scrambled shRNA sequence was used as negative control. Production of lentiviruses was performed in 293T cells as previously described³⁵. For virus transductions, a multiplicity of infection (MOI) of 20 was used in all experiments unless otherwise noted. Cells were transduced overnight in the presence of 0.5 µg mL⁻¹ polybrene, then rinsed with PBS and refreshed with new ECGM2 medium the next day. For analysis of knockdown effects, cells were used 2-4 days post-transduction. For Prox1 overexpression experiments, to generate programmed LECs (termed pLECs throughout the manuscript), cells were used at least 6 days after transduction to allow stable induction of the lymphatic phenotype. Prox1 overexpression in HUVECs resulted in at least 10-fold higher *PROX1* mRNA expression compared to HUVECs transduced with an empty control vector (data not shown). pLECs were used for many of the studies presented in the manuscript, as we

wished to investigate the role of FAO in VEC-to-LEC differentiation. Further, pLECs had similar levels of *CPT1A* mRNA and FAO flux induction compared to primary LECs, however other metabolic pathways require confirmation.

SIRNA-MEDIATED SILENCING: Prox1 siRNA-mediated knockdown was performed using Silencer® Select pre-designed siRNA from Applied Biosystems (Lennik, Belgium) as previously described⁸. Briefly, 5,000 cells were plated in 1.9 cm² wells and transfected after 24 hours growth with 5 pmol siRNA mixed with 0.5 µL of Lipofectamine 2000 (Life Technologies, Gent, Belgium) in 100 µL OPTI-MEM (Life Technologies). After overnight incubation, the transfection medium was replaced with ECGM2 and cells were maintained until day 3. Cells transfected with Silencer® negative control #1 were used as reference.

IN VITRO ASSAYS: Thymidine incorporation assay: Cell proliferation was determined by incubating cells for 24 hours with 1 µCi mL⁻¹ [³H]-thymidine. Cells were fixed with 100% ethanol for 15 min at 4 °C, then precipitated with 10% trichloroacetic acid and lysed with 0.1 N NaOH. The amount of [³H]-thymidine incorporated into DNA was measured by scintillation counting. Scratch wound migration assay: A scratch wound was applied on confluent monolayers (pretreated with 500 µg/mL MitoC overnight to mitotically inactivate the cells, allowing assessment of cell migration without the impact of proliferation) using a 200 µL pipette tip. After scratch wounding and image capture of the starting time point (T₀), cultures were further incubated with ECGM2 for 6-8 hours (until closure was almost reached in the control condition), and subsequent images were captured (T_x). Migration distance (gap area at T₀ minus gap area at T_x) was quantified using *NIH ImageJ* software and expressed as percentage closure. Spheroid sprouting assay: LECs were incubated overnight in hanging drops in ECGM2 containing methylcellulose (20% volume of a 1.2% methylcellulose solution prepared in ECBM2; Sigma-Aldrich) to form spheroids. Spheroids were then embedded in collagen gel as described⁶⁶ and cultured in ECGM2 supplemented with 100 ng mL⁻¹ recombinant human

VEGF-C (Peprotech, London, UK) for 24 hours to induce sprouting. Spheroid cultures were treated with 20 mM sodium acetate or 750 nM dNTP solution for 24 hours. Cultures were fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde at room temperature and imaged under brightfield using a Motic AE 31 microscope (Motic Electric Group Co Ltd, Xiamen, China) or Leica DMI6000 microscope (Leica Microsystems, Mannheim, Germany). Analysis of the number of sprouts per spheroid and the total sprout length (cumulative length of primary sprouts and branches per spheroid) was performed on phase contrast images using *NIH ImageJ* software. Cell survival: Cell survival was assessed by lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) release into the media using the LDH assay kit (Roche) as per manufacturer's specifications, whereby low LDH release signifies low cell death and high survival. 100 μ M etomoxir was used to verify whether pharmacological targeting of CPT1 could phenocopy the effects of CPT1a^{KD}. 5 mM BTC was used to test the effects of inhibition of SLC25A1. 0.38 μ M SGC-CBP30 was used to test the effects of inhibition of p300.

RNA ANALYSIS: RNA was collected and purified using the PureLink[®] RNA Mini Kit (Invitrogen) and converted to cDNA using the iScript cDNA synthesis kit (Bio-Rad). RNA expression was performed by Taqman quantitative RT-PCR using custom-made primers and probes, or premade primer sets (Applied Biosystems, Carlsbad, CA; or Integrated DNA Technologies, Inc., Leuven, Belgium). Human *HPRT1* was used as the control gene for all reactions and comparison with other common control genes (*β -ACTIN* and *GAPDH*) showed that *HPRT1* mRNA levels did not vary between experimental groups. Sequences of premade primer set ID numbers are available upon request.

ANALYSIS OF MOUSE EMBRYONIC DEVELOPMENT: At the appropriate day of embryonic development after vaginal plug, the pregnant mice were euthanized by cervical dislocation, and the uteri were removed. Blood flow/viability was assessed by counting the heart rate via either the yolk sac vessels or directly on the heart using a stereomicroscope. Embryos were dissected and the yolk sacs were washed 3 times with

PBS and used for verification of genotype and CPT1a gene excision. Embryos were fixed overnight in 1% paraformaldehyde at 4 °C, then washed with PBS before embedding in paraffin and serial sectioning from the level of the eye, progressing caudally until the liver. E10.5 embryo sections were selected by brightfield microscopy to identify the region of the cardinal vein just above the heart and sections were taken for immunohistochemical analysis from the region spanning the heart to the eye to identify all migrating LEC precursors. E12.5 and E14.5 embryo sections were selected by brightfield microscopy to identify the region from the base of the jugular vein where the jugular lymphatic sacs emerge spanning cranially beyond the end of the jugular lymphatic sacs, in total, encompassing a region of approximately 700 µm to assess the overall jugular lymphatic structure. For experiments assessing the role of etomoxir in mouse embryonic development, 30-40 mg kg⁻¹ etomoxir was injected intraperitoneally in pregnant dams daily from E8.5-10.5. A slight variation in the dosing of etomoxir (from the different sources listed in the Chemicals and Reagents section) was necessary after pilot experiments identified differences in efficacy between the different sources. Doses were titrated to comparable effects on lymphatic vasculature without inducing blood vascular effects or general developmental abnormalities. For E10.5 analysis, etomoxir was only injected from E8.5-9.5.

ANTIBODIES FOR IMMUNOHISTOCHEMISTRY: Rabbit anti-Prox1 (Angiobio, 11002P); rabbit anti-VEGFR3/Flt4 (eBioscience, 14-5988-82); anti-VEGFR3/Flt4 (R&D, AF743); mouse anti-CPT1a (Abcam, ab128568); rabbit anti-LYVE1 (Angiobio, 11-034); rabbit anti-acetyl histone H3 lysine 9 (Cell Signaling, 9659S); rat anti-CD31 (BD, 557355, MEC13.3); rat anti-TER119 (R&D, MAB1125); rat anti-BrdU (Serotec OBT, 0030). Appropriate AlexaFluor®-405, -488, -568 or -647 conjugated secondary antibodies were used (Molecular Probes). Tyramide signal amplification (TSA) kit was used as per manufacturer's specifications (Perkin Elmer). The enzymatic nature of amplification using the TSA kit precluded reliable assessment of immunoreactivity in immunostained slides of embryonic sections when maximal signal was obtained. Visualization of blood

vasculature was done using CD31 immunostaining (primary antibody see above) or by staining with isolectin GS-IB4-Alexa 647 (Molecular Probes).

ANALYSIS OF LEC PRECURSORS AND JUGULAR LYMPHATIC SACS: Confocal microscope images were captured of the dorsal region of cross sections of E10.5, 12.5 or 14.5 mouse embryos using a Zeiss LSM 780 confocal microscope (objectives: 310 with NA 0.3, 320 with NA 0.4; Carl Zeiss, Munich, Germany). For E10.5 embryos, as described above, a region focusing on the cardinal vein spanning the heart to the base of the eye was imaged to capture all levels where possible LEC precursors may emerge. To exclude blood vascular effects at the dose of etomoxir used, the area of the primary head vein and internal carotid artery (at the rostral extension of the dorsal aorta) were quantitated on haematoxylin & eosin stained serial sections in control and etomoxir-treated embryos. For E12.5 and E14.5 embryos, as described above, a region covering the majority of the jugular lymphatic sacs was taken to have an overall assessment of jugular lymphatic size/phenotype. At least 10 images of separate sections spanning this region were digitally captured, then LEC precursors were identified by staining for Prox1 and VEGFR3 and counted. Jugular lymphatic sac area (including JLS lumen) was determined by either VEGFR3 or LYVE1 positivity using *NIH ImageJ* software. Isolectin B4 was used to identify vascular structures (i.e. jugular vein, dorsal aorta, common carotid artery).

ANALYSIS OF ANTERIOR DORSAL DERMAL LYMPHATIC NETWORK: Pregnant dams between E15.5 to E16.5 were euthanized by cervical dislocation, embryos were dissected from the uterus, and gross embryo phenotype and heart rate were analyzed. The range of E15.5 and E16.5 was performed where EX.5 was considered as 10 AM, and harvesting and dissection lead to samples that were collected in a range of times between E15.5 and E16.5. Yolk sacs were collected, washed 3 times with PBS and used for genotyping, as described above. The embryos were then fixed in 1% PFA for 10 minutes before the dorsal skin was dissected, then the epidermal and dermal layers were separated under a

dissection microscope. Dissected back skins were then permeabilized (0.5% Triton-X-100, 0.01% sodium deoxycholate, 1% bovine serum albumin, 0.02% sodium azide) before being subjected to whole mount immunostaining. A combination of mosaic darkfield images (Leica DMI6000 microscope) and confocal images (Zeiss LSM780) were captured of the anterior dorsal dermal lymphatic network. *ANTERIOR DORSAL LYMPHATIC MORPHOMETRY*: Mosaic confocal images were captured of the anterior dorsal lymphatic network. The area of the midline gap was calculated by tracing using *NIH ImageJ* software, and expressed as area of gap relative to the total size of the image field. The total length of the lymphatic vascular network in these images was traced using *NIH ImageJ* software based on LYVE1 immunoreactivity (the small, intermixed LYVE1⁺ macrophage population in the dorsal skin was visually excluded). Branch points were defined as nodes of intersection of branches within the lymphatic network, and were manually counted with the assistance of the counter in the *NIH ImageJ* software. Average vessel thickness was calculated by tracing the width of all lymphatic sprouts using *NIH ImageJ* software at regular intervals in the entire anterior dorsal lymphatic network. *FILOPODIA*: Filopodia were assessed on high magnification confocal images of sprout tips at the growing lymphatic front, captured using a Zeiss LSM780 microscope. Immunostaining for LYVE1 and/or VEGFR3 was used to visualize filopodial extensions, which were counted manually with the assistance of *NIH ImageJ* software. LYVE1⁺ macrophages closely associated to growing lymphatic sprouts were excluded based on the plane of localization and also the lack of strong VEGFR3 positivity. *BRDU*: 100 mg kg⁻¹ BrdU was injected intraperitoneally in pregnant dams 2 hours before sacrifice. BrdU was detected by immunostaining, and co-stained with Prox1, VEGFR3 and Hoechst 33342 to allow visualization of the anterior dorsal lymphatic network. BrdU/Prox1 double-positive cells within the VEGFR3⁺ lymphatic network were assessed on high magnification mosaic confocal images captured using a Zeiss LSM780 microscope. Analysis was focused on the growing lymphatic front, as delineated by the first branch of the sprout in a network. Confocal stacks were used to ensure cells counted were within VEGFR3⁺ lymphatic structures, and data are expressed as the percentage of BrdU/Prox1 double-positive

cells relative to total Prox1⁺ cells. For filopodia and BrdU assessment in etomoxir-treated embryos, pregnant dams were given 40 mg kg⁻¹ etomoxir from E8.5-14.5.

ANALYSIS OF LYMPHATIC BEDS IN THE TRACHEA: Pregnant dams at E16.5 were euthanized by cervical dislocation, where E16.5 was considered as 10 AM. Embryos were dissected from the uterus, and gross embryo phenotype and heart rate were analyzed. Yolk sacs were collected, washed 3 times with PBS and used for genotyping, as described above. Trachea were then dissected from individual embryos and post-fixed for 1 to 2 hours in 1% paraformaldehyde, along with the tracheas. Organs were whole mount stained for LYVE1 for lymphatic vessels. Overview images of the immunostained organs were imaged using a Leica DMI6000 microscope, then high magnification mosaic confocal images captured using a Zeiss LSM780 microscope on specific regions of interest for quantitation. For quantification of tracheal lymphatic vessels, the vertical branches arising from the horizontal lymphatics following the cartilage/intercartilage rings were traced using *NIH ImageJ* software, and the average length of vertical branches was determined. Branch point quantitations in the lymphatics of the trachea were manually performed with the assistance of the counter in the *NIH ImageJ* software.

EVANS BLUE LYMPHANGIOGRAPHY IN E16.5 EMBRYOS: Pregnant dams were anaesthetized with ketamine/xylazine and the abdomen was opened to reveal the uterus. The uterus was cut open, and the yolk sac of individual embryos was dissected one at a time. The forepaw of the embryo was positioned under the dissecting microscope, 0.5 µL of 1% Evans blue was injected in the forepaw, and drainage of Evans blue was captured by video microscopy over a period of 10-15 minutes.

CORNEAL CAUTERIZATION LYMPHANGIOGENESIS ASSAY: The mouse corneal cauterization lymphangiogenesis assay was performed as previously described⁴⁰. Eight-week old female C57Bl/6 mice were purchased from Charles River and corneal neovascularization was induced by thermal cauterization. After anaesthetization with intraperitoneal injection of ketamine hydrochloride (100 mg kg⁻¹ body weight) and xylazine (10 mg kg⁻¹

body weight), the local anaesthetic (Unicaïne 0.4%; Thea Pharma, Wetteren, Belgium) was applied and the central cornea was thermally cauterized using an ophthalmic cautery (Optemp II V; Alcon Surgical, Fort Worth, TX). Mice were treated with intraperitoneal injections of 30 mg kg⁻¹ etomoxir and/or 400 µL of a 0.5 M sodium acetate solution daily, starting the day after corneal cauterization. Mice were euthanized at 9 days post-injury, eyes were removed and corneas were dissected. Whole-mounted corneas were fixed in 70% ethanol for 1 hour at room temperature and blocked with 3% BSA-3% Gloria milk (Nestlé, Brussels, Belgium) for 1 hour. Corneas were incubated overnight with polyclonal goat anti-mouse LYVE1 (R&D Systems, Abingdon, UK) and rat anti-mouse CD31 (BD Biosciences Pharmingen, San Jose, CA), then subsequently incubated with AlexaFluor® 488-conjugated rabbit anti-goat antibody and AlexaFluor® 546-conjugated goat anti-rat secondary antibodies (Molecular Probes, Merelbeke, Belgium) for 2 hours. Corneas were flat-mounted on a microscope slide with Vecta-shield mounting medium (Vector Laboratories, Burlingame, CA) and imaged using a Leica DMI6000 microscope (Leica Microsystems, Mannheim, Germany).

IMMUNOBLOT ANALYSIS: Protein extraction and immunoblot analysis was performed using a modified RIPA buffer (50 mM Tris-HCL pH 8.0, 150 mM NaCl, 1% Triton X-100, 0.1% SDS, 1% deoxycholate acid) in the presence of dithiothreitol (DTT; Pierce), protease and phosphatase inhibitors (Roche, Vilvoorde, Belgium) as well as HDAC inhibitors (sodium butyrate and trichostatin A (TSA; Sigma). Lysates were separated by SDS-PAGE under reducing conditions, transferred to a nitrocellulose membrane, and analyzed by immunoblotting. Primary antibodies used were rabbit anti-Prox1 (11067-2) from Proteintech, rabbit anti-acetyl histone H3 (lysine 9) antibody (9671), rabbit anti-CPT1a (D3B3) antibody (11252) and rabbit anti-β-actin (4967) from Cell Signaling, rabbit anti-pan-acetyl histone H3 antibody (39139) from Active Motif, and rabbit anti-VEGFR3 (C-20) antibody (sc-321) and rabbit anti-p300 (N-15) antibody (sc-584) from Santa Cruz. Appropriate secondary antibodies were from Cell Signaling. Signal was detected using the ECL system (Amersham Biosciences, GE Healthcare, Diegem, Belgium) according to

the manufacturer's instructions. Unless otherwise indicated, β -actin was used as loading control. Densitometric quantifications of bands were done with *NIH Image J* software.

HISTONE EXTRACTION: Cells were collected, washed with cold PBS, and resuspended in cold NIB buffer (15 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.5, 60 mM KCl, 15 mM NaCl, 5 mM MgCl₂, 1 mM CaCl₂, 250 mM sucrose, freshly added: 1 mM DTT, 1x protease inhibitors, 10 mM sodium butyrate, 0.1% NP-40). Nuclei were pelleted at 600 rcf for 5 min at 4 °C and washed using NIB buffer without NP-40. The pellets were immediately resuspended in 0.4 N H₂SO₄ and rotated for at least 30 min at 4 °C. After centrifugation at 11,000 rcf for 10 min at 4 °C, histones were precipitated from the supernatant by addition of 20% trichloroacetic acid (TCA) for at least 1 hour, followed by centrifugation at 16,000 rcf for 10 min at 4 °C. The pellet was washed with acetone. Histone proteins were resuspended in 0.1 N NaOH.

PALMITATE INCORPORATION INTO HISTONE FRACTION: For determination of palmitate incorporation into histone fraction, cells were incubated with 100 μ Ci mL⁻¹ (0.65 μ M final concentration) [U-¹⁴C]-palmitic acid for 1-2 days before acidic extraction of histones, as detailed above. The specific activity of the [U-¹⁴C]-palmitic acid solutions was normalized based on the concentration of tracer added. A portion of the resuspended histone fraction was taken for protein quantification by the BCA method for normalization, and the remainder was used to determine radioactivity in the acidic histone fraction by scintillation counting.

CHROMATIN IMMUNOPRECIPITATION

Chromatin immunoprecipitation-sequencing: Cultured cells were fixed by adding 1% formaldehyde (16% formaldehyde (w/v), Methanol-free, Thermo Scientific) directly to the medium for 8 min. Glycine (150 μ M) was added for 5 min to quench the formaldehyde. Cells were washed twice with ice-cold PBS 0.5% Triton-X100, scraped and collected by centrifugation (1000 \times G for 5 min at 4 °C). The pellet was resuspended in 1400 μ L of RIPA buffer (50 mM Tris-HCl pH 8, 150 mM NaCl, 2 mM EDTA pH 8, 1%

Triton-X100, 0.5% Sodium deoxycholate, 1% SDS, 1% protease inhibitors). The lysate was homogenized by passing through an insulin syringe, and incubated on ice for 10 min. The chromatin was kept ice-cold and sonicated for 3 min by using a 250 Digital Sonifier (Branson) with 0.7 s 'On' and 1.3 s 'Off' pulses at 40% power amplitude, yielding a DNA fragment size of 100 to 500 bp. The samples were centrifuged (10 min at 16000 × G at 4 °C) and supernatants transferred to a new eppendorf tube. 50 µL of sheared chromatin was set apart as "input", and 5 µg of either rabbit anti-FLAG (Pierce), rabbit anti-Prox1 (ProteinTech), rabbit anti-p300 antibody (Santa Cruz) or rabbit anti-H3K9ac (Cell Signaling) antibody was added to the remainder of the chromatin. Samples were incubated overnight at 4 °C on a rotator. 20 µL Pierce Protein A/G Magnetic Beads (Life Technologies) were added to the samples and incubated at 4 °C for at least 5 hours. A/G Magnetic Beads were collected and washed 5 times with washing buffer (50 mM Tris-HCl, 200 mM LiCl, 2 mM EDTA, pH 8, 1% Triton, 0.5% Sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS, 1% protease inhibitors), and twice with TE buffer. The A/G magnetic beads were resuspended in 50 µL of TE buffer, and 1.5 µL of RNase A (200 units, NEB, Ipswich, MA, USA) was added to the A/G beads samples and to the input, followed by incubation for 10 min at 37 °C. After addition of 1.5 µL of proteinase K (NEB, 200 units) and overnight incubation at 65 °C, the DNA was purified using 1.8 × volume of Agencourt AMPure XP (Beckman Coulter) according to the manufacturer's specifications, and then eluted in 30 µL of TE buffer. Input and immunoprecipitated DNA was transformed into libraries using the NEBNext Ultra DNA library prep kit for Illumina (NEB), and amplified using KAPA HiFi HotStart ReadyMix for 14 cycles. Libraries were purified according to the manufacturer's instructions, and processed for high-throughput sequencing on an Illumina HiSeq 2500. Resultant FastQ files were mapped to the human genome (build GRCh37/hg19) using bowtie (version 0.12.8; settings -v 2 -m 1 -p --best -S). Summarized and raw data are included in Supplementary Tables 1 and 2. As well, the raw data is available online via the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) under reference number GSE71230 for reviewer access via the following link:

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?token=qvktSomiftuxnah&acc=GSE712>

30

Model-based analysis of ChIP-sequencing: Peaks were called in Prox1-FLAG ChIP-seq data by model-based analysis of ChIP-sequencing (MACS)⁶⁷⁻⁶⁹, using libraries of FLAG-ChIP on cells transfected with the empty overexpression plasmid as background data set. Experiments were run in biological duplicates, with a strong correlation between both (Pearson's $r = 0.79$). Peaks were further validated by endogenous Prox1 ChIP-seq, which again showed strong correlation with Prox1-FLAG ChIP-seq data (Pearson's $r = 0.68$). To call H3K9ac peaks, MACS was applied on pooled H3K9ac data using the input as background set. Read counts at H3K9ac peak areas were quantified in each sample using SeqMonk, and background-normalized to assess enrichment⁶⁸. Seqmonk was also used to annotate peaks with genes, with peaks being assigned to the nearest gene within 5 kb. Differential acetylation at these peaks between two groups was assessed with EdgeR⁶⁹, computing exact tests for differences in the means of negative-binomially distributed counts in 3 independent biological replicates. We called peak areas as differentially acetylated when the corresponding false discovery rate (FDR)-adjusted p-value was below 0.10.

Chromatin immunoprecipitation for PCR: Chromatin immunoprecipitation (ChIP) was performed using the EZ ChIP™ kit (Upstate) or the ChIP-seq collection protocol listed above. For the EZ ChIP™ kit, samples were fixed with 1% formaldehyde (Thermo Scientific), then washed with cold PBS, scraped and collected in cold PBS containing 1x protease inhibitor cocktail. After resuspending the cell pellet in SDS lysis buffer (containing cocktail, sodium butyrate and TSA) and sonication, samples were incubated with either rabbit IgG (Jackson Immunologicals), rabbit anti-Prox1 (Proteintech), rabbit anti-FLAG antibody (Pierce), rabbit anti-p300 (Santa Cruz) or rabbit anti-acetylated histone H3 (lysine 9; Cell Signaling) and processed as per manufacturer's specifications. The input, control IgG and immunoprecipitated PCR/qPCR: DNA fractions were either subjected to PCR and run on a 2% agarose gel or subjected to quantitative PCR using

SYBR Green. For PCR gels, band intensities were quantitated using *NIH ImageJ* software. Primer sequences are available upon request.

Luciferase reporter constructs: Sequences verified by PCR or qPCR were cloned into the pGL3 basic luciferase plasmid (Promega) lacking promoter and enhancer elements. HUVECs were transduced with control lentiviruses or FLAG-Prox1 lentiviruses. Four days after viral transduction, cells were trypsinized and transfected with empty pGL3 plasmids or plasmids containing sequences of Prox1 enrichment, as identified by CHIP-seq, using Nucleofector transfection reagent (Lonza), as per manufacturer's specifications. Cells were co-transfected with the respective luciferase reporters and also the Renilla plasmid, as a control, and allowed to grow for 48 hours before being collected with PBS, centrifuged, then lysed. Luciferase activity was measured by Dual Luciferase Reporter Kit (Promega) according to the manufacturer's specifications.

MASS SPECTROMETRY

Detection of acetyl-CoA and CoA: Cells were seeded in 6 well plates and at appropriate time points, samples were collected in 300 μ L 1% PCA/ well (Perchloric acid, Sigma). Analytes were separated on a Dionex Ultimate 3000 UPLC (Thermo Scientific) equipped with a reversed-phase Atlantis dC18 column (2.1 mm x 150 mm, pore size 5 μ m, Waters) in-line connected to a Q-Exactive OrbiTRAP mass spectrometer (Thermo Scientific). The column was thermostatted at 37 °C, samples were kept at 8 °C in the autosampler. The LC-MS analysis was adapted from previously published methods³⁶. Briefly, 5 mM ammonium acetate in water was used as solvent A, 5 mM ammonium acetate in 95/5 acetonitrile/water (%v/v) as solvent B, and 80/20/0.1 (%v/v/v) acetonitrile/water/formic acid as solvent C. Gradient conditions were set as follows: 2% B for 1.5 min, increased to 25% over 3.5 min, increased to 100% B in 0.5 min and held for 8.5 min, washed with 100% C for 5 min, before equilibration for 5 min. The flow rate was 200 μ L min⁻¹. Of each sample 100 μ L was injected onto the LC-MS, the mass spec operated in positive ESI mode. The OrbiTRAP used both SIM mode (following ions of coenzyme A: m/z 768.12248 and acetyl-CoA: m/z 810.13305) as well as targeted MS2 mode for the

validation of the identified ions in SIM mode (collision energy was set at 35 eV, fragment ion 136.06 corresponding to the adenine moiety was used for validation of the CoA species). The column effluent was diverted to the mass spectrometer from 2 to 13 min and to waste for the remainder of the run. The mass spectrometer conditions were as follows: ion spray voltage (5.0 kV), sheath gas flow rate 35, auxiliary gas flow rate 10, capillary temperature 450 °C, S-lens RF level 50, auxiliary gas heater temperature 300 °C.

Detection of metabolite pools and isotopomer labelling by LC-MS: Metabolites were extracted in 250 µL of a 50:30:20 (methanol:acetonitrile:10 mM Tris, pH 9.3) extraction buffer. Extraction samples were then centrifuged for 5 min at 20,000 x G and the supernatant was transferred to LC-MS vials. Targeted measurements of GSSG, GSH, NADP⁺, NADPH, citrate, isocitrate, alpha-ketoglutarate, fumarate, malate, aspartate, glutamate, UTP, dATP, dTTP and were performed using a Dionex UltiMate 3000 LC System (Thermo Scientific) coupled to a Q Exactive Orbitrap mass spectrometer (Thermo Scientific) operated in negative mode. Practically, 35 µL of sample was injected on a SeQuant ZIC/ pHILIC Polymeric column (Merck Millipore). The gradient started with 20% of solvent B (10 mM NH₄-acetate in m_qH₂O, pH 9.3) and 80% solvent A (LC-MS grade acetonitrile) and remained at 20% B until 2 min post injection. Next, a linear gradient to 80% B was carried out until 29 min. At 38 min the gradient returned to 40% B followed by a decrease to 20% B at 42 min. The chromatography was stopped at 58 min. The flow was kept constant at 100 µL/min at the column was placed at 25 °C throughout the analysis.

The MS was operated both in targeted MS2 mode using a spray voltage of 3.5 kV, capillary temperature of 320 °C, sheath gas at 10.0, auxiliary gas at 5.0. For the targeted MS2 mode, AGC was set at 2e5, maximum IT at 100 ms, a resolution of 17.500 and an isolation window of 1.2 m/z. Data collection was performed using *Xcalibur* software (Thermo Scientific).

ATP, ADP, AMP (for energy charge): Cells were washed with 0.9% NaCl (at 4 °C) and extracted in 250 µL 80% methanol (stored at -80 °C). Next, extracts were transferred to an eppendorf tube and centrifuged at 20,000 x G for 5 min at 4 °C to remove precipitated proteins and insolubilities. Measurement of ATP, ADP and AMP was performed using a Dionex UltiMate 3000 LC System (Thermo Scientific) coupled to a Q Exactive Orbitrap mass spectrometer (Thermo Scientific) operated in negative ionization mode. Practically, 20 µL of sample was injected on a SeQuant ZIC/ pHILIC Polymeric column (Merck Millipore). The gradient started with 10% of solvent B (10 mM NH₄-acetate in mQH₂O, pH 9.3) and 90% solvent A (acetonitrile, LC-MS grade) and remained at 10% B until 2 min post injection. Next, a linear gradient to 80% B was carried out until 29 min. At 38 min the gradient returned to 40% B followed by a decrease to 10% B at 42 min. The chromatography was stopped at 58 min. The flow was maintained at 100 µL min⁻¹ and the column was kept at 25°C throughout the analysis. The MS (Q-Exactive, Thermo Scientific) operated both in full scan mode using a spray voltage of 3.2 kV, capillary temperature of 320°C, sheath gas at 20.0, auxiliary gas at 5.0. For Full scan - SIM mode, AGC target was set at 1e6 using a resolution of 140.000, with a maximum IT of 512 ms. Data collection was performed using Xcalibur software (Thermo Scientific), values of ATP, ADP and AMP represent the area under the curve of the measured ions (m/z ATP 505.98793; ADP 426.02160; AMP 346.05526) with a maximum allowed relative mass deviation of 5 ppm. To calculate concentrations of ATP, ADP and AMP, a standard curve was generated using ATP, ADP and AMP (Sigma) diluted in H₂O to 100 mM, then serially diluted in a 50:30:20 mixture of methanol:acetonitrile:Tris-HCl (10 mM, pH 9.3) over a range from 0.1 µM – 10 mM. This standard curve was used to calculate concentrations of ATP, ADP and AMP over a lineage range (correlation co-efficient (R²) > 0.997 – 0.999). To estimate the concentration per cell, we assumed that the volume of a single EC was 2 x 10⁻¹² L³⁷. ATP, ADP and AMP concentrations were in line with previously published reports (not shown)³⁷⁻³⁹. Energy charge was calculated as (ATP + ½ ADP) / (ATP + ADP + AMP)⁴⁰.

METABOLIC ASSAYS

Radioisotope tracer experiments: ECs were seeded and allowed to attach before washing and incubation for 6 hours in ECGM2 containing $0.4 \mu\text{Ci mL}^{-1}$ (24.24 nM final concentration) $[5\text{-}^3\text{H}]\text{-glucose}$ (Perkin Elmer) or $2 \mu\text{Ci mL}^{-1}$ (66.67 nM final concentration) $[9,10\text{-}^3\text{H}]\text{-palmitate}$ (Perkin Elmer) for assessment of glycolytic or fatty acid β -oxidation (FAO) flux, respectively. For FAO flux assay, $50 \mu\text{M}$ of L-carnitine solution was supplemented to the media. To assess the production of $^3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, after a cumulative 24 hours after plating cells, media was transferred to glass vials and sealed with rubber stoppers. $^3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was captured in hanging wells within the glass vials containing Whatman filter paper soaked with H_2O over a period of 48 hours at $37 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to reach saturation⁷¹. 100 ng mL^{-1} recombinant human VEGF-C was used to test its effect on FAO flux. $5 \mu\text{M}$ MAZ51 was used to test the effect of VEGFR3 inhibition on FAO flux. Palmitate uptake was assessed by incubation with $2 \mu\text{Ci mL}^{-1}$ (66.67 nM final concentration) $[9,10\text{-}^3\text{H}]\text{-palmitate}$ (Perkin Elmer) for 30 min before washing 5 times with PBS, followed by cell lysis with 0.1 N NaOH . Radioactivity for radioisotope tracer studies was determined by liquid scintillation counting.

INTRACELLULAR ROS ANALYSIS: Intracellular ROS levels were measured using CM-H₂DCFDA dye (Invitrogen) according to manufacturer's specifications. H₂O₂ measurements were performed using Amplex Red (Invitrogen) according to manufacturer's specifications.

COMPUTERIZED METHODS OF QUANTITATION IN THE CORNEAL CAUTERIZATION MODEL:

Computerized quantitation of the corneal lymphatic vessel network was performed with the toolbox of Matlab R2013a (8.1.0.604) software, as previously described⁴¹. Image processing algorithms were used to extract lymphatic vessels from the background. The resultant binary image, where lymphatic vessels were represented as white pixels (pixels value equal to 1) on a black background (pixels value equal to 0), was subjected to automated measurements: (1) area density defined as the surface covered by vessels

relative to the total cornea area; (2) end point density defined as the number of vessel extremities per corneal area; (3) branching density, defined as the number of vessel bifurcations / intersections per corneal area; and (4) length density, which represents the cumulative length of the lymphatic vessel network.

IMAGE QUANTITATION OF VEGFR3 AND H3K9AC IN THE CORNEAL CAUTERIZATION MODEL:

Image quantitation on whole mount immunostained corneas was possible, as no amplification step was used for the immunostaining protocols. The average intensity of VEGFR3 immunoreactivity in the lymphatic vessels in the corneal cauterization assay were calculated using *NIH ImageJ* software on 63x magnification confocal images captured using a LSM 780 confocal microscope (Carl Zeiss). A sum of the slices of the confocal stack were projected, and the border of the lymphatic network was circled using the polygon drawing tool. The average intensity of the area was calculated for a minimum of 5 sprouts per cornea. The tracing of the lymphatic sprout from this analysis was subsequently used to delineate the lymphatic vessel borders to identify the H3K9ac-positive LECs. Briefly, using the original confocal stack, nuclei (as identified by Hoechst 33342 staining) clearly within the lymphatic sprout were identified. These individual nuclei were circled, and the average corrected total cell fluorescence (CTCF = integrated density - (area x mean background fluorescence intensity))⁴² was determined per sprout. For all images in a single experiment, the samples were all stained at the same time, and microscope capture settings were kept constant for all image capture.

STATISTICS: Data are represented as mean \pm SEM of 3 independent experiments unless otherwise stated. For *in vitro* experiments with HUVECs or HDLECs, a minimum of three independent experiments using different donors was performed. No statistical methods were used to pre-determine sample size. For embryo experiments, power calculation was performed based on results from a pilot study at E14.5 (minimum n = 4 required). For cornea experiments, sample size was determined based on previous experience with the model⁴⁰. No randomization was necessary as animals were analyzed at basal

conditions. Unless otherwise indicated, statistical significance between multiple groups was determined by ANOVA to ensure comparable variance, then individual comparisons performed by Bonferroni post-hoc test (Prism v6.0f, GraphPad Software, Inc., La Jolla, CA, USA). Statistical significance between two groups was determined by standard two-tailed t-test with F-testing to confirm equality of variance (Prism). Comparison of gene ontology sets was assessed using Chi-square test (Prism). $p < 0.05$ was considered as statistically significant. A q-value of 0.1 (false discovery rate (FDR)-corrected p-value) was used for CHIP-seq experiments to determine differentially acetylated genes.

DATA AVAILABILITY: Sequencing data are available at the Gene Expression Omnibus under accession [GSE71230](#).

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LEGENDS TO EXTENDED DATA FIGURES

EXTENDED DATA FIGURE 1: LECs HAVE HIGHER EXPRESSION OF FATTY ACID β -OXIDATION AND TRANSPORT PROTEINS

a, Quantitative RT-PCR analysis of the mRNA levels of carnitine palmitoyltransferase (*CPT1A*, *CPT1B*, *CPT1C* and *CPT2*) relative to the housekeeping gene *HPRT1* in VECs and LECs (n = 3). **b-f**, Fold change in the mRNA levels of fatty acid binding protein (*FABP4* (b), *FABP5* (c), fatty acid transfer protein (*FATP3*) (d), *FATP4* (e) and *CD36* (fatty acid translocase, *FAT*) (f) in LECs versus VECs (n = 3). **g**, Fold change in *PROX1* mRNA expression in LECs silenced for Prox1 (siProx1) versus control silenced LECs (ctrl) (n = 3). Mean \pm s.e.m. of n independent experiments. Statistical test: t-test was used for comparison of two groups. *p<0.05, NS = not statistically significant.

EXTENDED DATA FIGURE 2: CPT1A GENE EXCISION IN PROX1^{ΔCPT1A} EMBRYOS AND ADDITIONAL PHENOTYPIC INFORMATION AND KINETICS OF LOSS OF CPT1A *IN VIVO* AND *IN VITRO*

a, Genotyping for the presence of the CPT1a floxed (2,200 bp) and excision band (300 bp) in E14.5 Prox1^{ΔCPT1a} embryos. **b**, Cartoon of anatomical orientation of the dorsal aorta (DA) and jugular vein (JV) with respect to the jugular lymphatic sacs (JLS). The red dotted lines in the embryo drawing indicate the jugular region of focus in WT E14.5 mouse embryos. SC, spinal cord; VB, vertebral body. **c,d**, Staining for CPT1a (magenta) and VEGFR3 (green) in WT (Prox1) and Prox1^{ΔCPT1a} embryos at E14.5. CPT1a immunoreactivity (magenta) is seen within VEGFR3⁺ LECs (green) of the JLS in WT embryos (c). In the JLS of the E14.5 Prox1^{ΔCPT1a} embryo (d), CPT1a immunoreactivity is undetectable. For the CPT1a signal channel only (left panels), a higher magnification is shown than for the VEGFR3 signal channel (top right panels) or the merged signal (bottom right panels). The white dashed lines denote endothelium in the JLS. Arrows denote LECs without apparent CPT1a immunoreactivity. Scale bars: 5 μm. **e**, Genotyping for the presence of the CPT1a floxed (2,200 bp) and excision band (300 bp) in E9.5 Prox1^{FKΔCPT1a} embryos. **f,g**, Representative micrographs of staining for CPT1a (magenta) and VEGFR3 (green) in LECs within the jugular lymphatic sac (JLS) at E11.5 in a WT (f) and Prox1^{ΔCPT1a} (g) embryo. Top panels show the single channel CPT1a signal. The insets represent an overlay of CPT1a and VEGFR3 signals (bottom left f,g) and the single channel signal for VEGFR3 (bottom right f,g). Dashed white lines outline the endothelium of the JLS, as identified by VEGFR3 staining. Arrows highlight areas within the lymphatic endothelium with strong CPT1a-immunoreactivity in VEGFR3⁺ cells within the JLS of a WT embryo (f) and weaker but still detectable CPT1a-immunoreactive signal in VEGFR3⁺ cells within the JLS in a Prox1^{ΔCPT1a} embryo (g). **h**, Primary antibody omission for CPT1a and VEGFR3. Isolectin B4 (blue) was used to highlight vascular structures in the negative control (WT E14.5 embryo), and the JLS characteristically was more weakly stained compared to the jugular vein (upper panel). As expected, primary antibody omission (VEGFR3 (488, middle panel); CPT1a (Cy5, lower panel)) revealed no aspecific immunoreactivity. **i,j**, Representative micrographs of staining for CPT1a (magenta) and

VEGFR3 (green) in LECs within the jugular lymphatic sac (JLS) at E11.5 in $Prox1^{FK\Delta CPT1a}$ (i) and $Flt4^{\Delta CPT1a}$ (j) embryo. The left panels show the single channel CPT1a signal. The insets represent an overlay of CPT1a and VEGFR3 signals (upper i,j), the single channel signal for VEGFR3 (bottom left i,j) and the primary antibody omission for CPT1a (bottom right i,j). As expected, primary antibody omission revealed no aspecific immunoreactivity. Dashed white lines outline the endothelium of the JLS, as identified by VEGFR3 staining. Arrows highlight areas within the lymphatic endothelium with still detectable CPT1a-immunoreactive signal in $VEGFR3^+$ cells within the JLS in a $Prox1^{FK\Delta CPT1a}$ (i) and $Flt4^{\Delta CPT1a}$ (j) embryo. Scale bars: 10 μ m. **k**, Genotyping for the presence of the CPT1a floxed (2,200 bp) and excision band (300 bp) in E9.5 $Prox1^{\Delta CPT1a}$ embryos. **l**, Quantitative RT-PCR analysis of *CPT1A* mRNA expression at 1-3 days after $CPT1a^{KD}$ in VECs (n = 3). **m**, Densitometric quantification of immunoblotted CPT1a protein relative to β -actin at 1-4 days after $CPT1a^{KD}$ in VECs, illustrating that, likely due of the CPT1a protein stability, as much as 35-40% residual CPT1a protein levels were still detectable at 3 days after silencing CPT1a (n = 3). **n**, Representative stereomicroscope images of E10.5 WT (left) and $VEcad^{\Delta CPT1a}$ (right) embryos after tamoxifen administration from E7.5-9.5, showing severe developmental and vascular abnormalities in embryos. **o,p**, Representative micrograph of staining for CPT1a (magenta) and VEGFR3 (green) in an E16.5 $Prox1^{FK\Delta CPT1a}$ (o) and $Flt4^{\Delta CPT1a}$ (p) embryo. Compared to CPT1a immunoreactivity seen within the $VEGFR3^+$ LECs of the JLS in WT embryos (Extended Data Fig. 2c), CPT1a immunoreactivity is undetectable in LECs of E16.5 $Prox1^{FK\Delta CPT1a}$ (o) and $Flt4^{\Delta CPT1a}$ (p) embryos (left panels). The right panels represent the single channel signal for VEGFR3 (top right) and the merged signal for CPT1a and VEGFR3 (bottom right), highlighting the lack of detectable CPT1a immunoreactivity in mutant embryos. The white dashed lines denote the lymphatic endothelium in the JLS. Arrows denote LECs without apparent CPT1a immunoreactivity. Of note, due to our TSA-based amplification method for all of our immunostaining protocols of embryo sections (see Methods), the VEGFR3 immunoreactivity seen in panels o and p was maximally enhanced, which is why VEGFR3 immunoreactivity does not appear lower for the gene

deficient embryos compared to WT shown in Extended Data Fig. 2c. Scale bars: 5 μm . Mean \pm s.e.m. Statistical test: *t*-test was used for comparison of two groups. * $p < 0.05$, NS = not statistically significant.

EXTENDED DATA FIGURE 3: EARLY AND LATER-STAGE LYMPHATIC-SPECIFIC LOSS OF CPT1A RESULTS IN DEFECTS IN LYMPHATIC DEVELOPMENT

a, Representative stereomicrographs of an E14.5 Prox1 (left) and a Prox1^{ΔCPT1a} embryo with deletion of CPT1a in Prox1-positive ECs (right). Asterisks denote subdermal edema. Arrows highlight subdermal bleeding spots. **b**, Zoomed in micrograph of the Prox1^{ΔCPT1a} embryo shown in panel a (right). Arrows denote bleeding spots. **c**, Representative micrograph of TER119 immunostaining (green) of erythroid precursors (arrows) present within the JLS of a Prox1^{ΔCPT1a} embryo, as highlighted by LYVE1 staining (red). Dotted lines denote endothelium in lymphatic structures. Scale bar: 100 μm. **d**, Zoomed in micrograph of lymphatic capillaries of an E16.5 Prox1^{ΔCPT1a} embryo, visualized by Evans blue dye injection (blue) in the forepaws. Arrows indicate blood-filled blunt-ended dermal lymphatic structures. **e-o**, Experiments involving the anterior dorsal dermal lymphatic vessels of E15.5 WT (Prox1) and Prox1^{ΔCPT1a} embryos. **e**, Immunostaining for LYVE1⁺ lymphatic vessels. White dashed lines: left/right lymphatic front. Lower panels: high magnification images of red boxed regions. Scale bars: 500 μm. **f**, Quantitation of the lymphatic vessel outgrowth towards the midline in the anterior dorsal back skin, as measured by the average remaining gap between left and right flank lymphatics (n = 6 embryos for WT; n = 9 embryos for Prox1^{ΔCPT1a}; 3 litters). **g-i**, Quantification of the total vessel length relative to the total field area (g), number of branch points (corrected for lymphatic length) (h) and average vessel width (i) (n = 6 embryos for WT; n = 9 embryos for Prox1^{ΔCPT1a}; 3 litters). **j**, LYVE1⁺ dermal lymphatic vessels in an E15.5 Prox1^{ΔCPT1a} embryo or an E16.5 Prox1^{FKΔCPT1a} embryo highlighting the presence of lymphatic islands (white arrows). Scale bars: 500 μm. **k-m**, Experiments involving the anterior dorsal dermal lymphatic vessels of E15.5 WT (Prox1) and Prox1^{ΔCPT1a} embryos treated with tamoxifen from E10.5-12.5 to inactivate CPT1a in LECs after initial lymphatic structure formation has occurred. **k**, Immunostaining for LYVE1⁺ lymphatic vessels. White dashed lines: left/right lymphatic front. Lower panels: high magnification images of red boxed regions. Scale bars: 500 μm. **l**, Quantitation of the lymphatic vessel outgrowth towards the midline in the anterior dorsal back skin, as measured by the average remaining gap

between left and right flank lymphatics (n = 5 embryos for WT; n = 6 embryos for Prox1^{ΔCPT1a}; 2 litters). **m**, Quantification of the total vessel length relative to the total field area (n = 5 embryos for WT; n = 6 embryos for Prox1^{ΔCPT1a}; 2 litters). **n-p**, Experiments involving the anterior dorsal dermal lymphatic network in E15.5 WT (Prox1) and Prox1^{ΔCPT1a} embryos. **n**, High magnification images of VEGFR3⁺ (green) lymphatic sprouts. The white arrows indicate filopodia. Note the weaker VEGFR3 immunoreactive signal in the Prox1^{ΔCPT1a} embryo (right panel). Inset panels represent LYVE1 staining, confirming the identification of filopodia by another marker (note that LYVE1 also stains macrophages, which are sometimes in the proximity of lymphatic sprouts, but clearly distinguishable based on their morphology). Scale bars: 10 μm. **o**, Number of filopodia per lymphatic sprout tip (n = 6 embryos for WT; n = 9 embryos for Prox1^{ΔCPT1a}; 3 litters). **p**, VEGFR3 (white) immunoreactivity in the growing dorsal dermal lymphatic vessels. Note the weaker VEGFR3 immunoreactive signal in the Prox1^{ΔCPT1a} embryo (right panel). Scale bars: 100 μm. Mean ± s.e.m. Statistical test: *t*-test was used for comparison of two groups. **p*<0.05.

EXTENDED DATA FIGURE 4: LYMPHATIC-SPECIFIC LOSS OF CPT1A RESULTS IN DEFECTS IN TRACHEAL LYMPHATIC DEVELOPMENT, FLT4-DRIVEN LOSS OF CPT1A PHENOCOPIES PROX1-DRIVEN EXCISION AND PHARMACOLOGICAL INHIBITION OF FAO INDUCES LYMPHATIC DEFECTS AT LATER STAGES OF EMBRYONIC DEVELOPMENT

a-c, Investigation of lymphatic growth in the trachea of E16.5 WT (Prox1) and Prox1^{ΔCPT1a} embryos. **a,** LYVE1⁺ lymphatic structures in the trachea. Scale bars: 200 μm. Bottom panels: high magnification images of regions denoted by the white boxes. In the trachea, lymphatic vessels first grow horizontally, after which sprouts branch off vertically (white arrows). Note the underdevelopment of lymphatic growth in the mutant embryo (yellow arrowheads). **b,c,** Quantitation of the average length of vertical connections (b) and average number of branch points (c) (n = 6 embryos for WT; n = 5 embryos for Prox1^{ΔCPT1a}; 2 litters). **d-i,** Experiments in E16.5 WT control (Flt4) and Flt4^{ΔCPT1a} embryos. **d,** Genotyping for the presence of the CPT1a floxed (2,200 bp) and excision band (300 bp) at E11.5. **e,** LYVE1⁺ dorsal dermal lymphatic vessels. White dashed lines: left/right lymphatic front. Bottom panels: high magnification insets of red boxed region. Note that LYVE1 also stains macrophages. Scale bars: 500 μm. **f,** Quantitation of the lymphatic vessel outgrowth towards the midline, as measured by the average remaining gap between left and right flank lymphatics (n = 7 embryos for Flt4; n = 8 embryos for Flt4^{ΔCPT1a}; 2 litters). **g-i,** Quantitation of the total vessel length (normalized per total area) (g), number of branch points (corrected for lymphatic length) (h) and average vessel width (i) (n = 7 embryos for Flt4; n = 8 embryos for Flt4^{ΔCPT1a}; 2 litters). **j-x,** Embryonic phenotype of vehicle- (ctrl) or etomoxir-treated (eto) embryos. **j,** Representative stereomicrographs at E14.5. Asterisks denote subdermal edema. **k,** VEGFR3 immunostaining in the jugular region of E14.5 embryos. solid white line: jugular vein (JV); dashed white line: jugular lymphatic sac (JLS). Scale bars: 50 μm. **l,** JLS area in E14.5 embryos (n = 8 embryos for ctrl; n = 5 embryos for eto; 1 litter for each group). **m-s,** Analysis of E16.5 ctrl- or eto-treated embryos. **m,** LYVE1⁺ dermal lymphatic vessels. White dashed lines: indicate the left/right lymphatic front. Scale bars: 500 μm. **n-q,** Lymphatic vessel outgrowth (n), total lymphatic vessel length (normalized per total

image area; o), number of lymphatic branch points (corrected for lymphatic length; p), and average lymphatic vessel width (q) (n = 6 embryos for ctrl; n = 6 embryos for eto; 2 litters). **r**, Quantitation of the number of filopodia per lymphatic sprout tip (n = 5 embryos for ctrl; n = 6 embryos for eto; 2 litters per group). **s**, The number of proliferating BrdU⁺ LECs in E15.5 ctrl and etomoxir (eto) embryos (n = 4 embryos for ctrl; n = 6 embryos for eto; 1 litter per group). **t**, Quantitation of the vascular area in primary head vein (left and right side) and the internal carotid artery (rostral extension of the dorsal aorta; left and right side) in E10.5 ctrl- and eto-treated embryos. **u-x**, Quantitation of the lymphatic vessel outgrowth (u), total lymphatic vessel length (v), the number of lymphatic branch points (w), and average lymphatic vessel width (x) in the dorsal dermal lymphatic network in E15.5 embryos treated from embryonic day (E)8.5-14.5 with vehicle (ctrl^{E8.5-14.5}) or etomoxir (eto^{E8.5-14.5}) (n = 6 embryos for ctrl^{E8.5-14.5}; n = 5 embryos for eto^{E8.5-14.5}). Mean ± s.e.m.. Statistical test: ANOVA and Bonferroni post-hoc test were used in multiple group comparisons. *t*-test was used for comparison of two groups. *p<0.05, NS = not statistically significant.

EXTENDED DATA FIGURE 5: CONFIRMATION OF CPT1A^{KD} USING A SECOND SHRNA, ADDITIONAL EFFECTS OF CPT1A^{KD}, SILENCING ANOTHER FAO GENE IN LECs, CPT1A OVEREXPRESSION DOES NOT INDUCE THE EXPRESSION OF LEC MARKERS AND CPT1A^{KD} IN VECs DOES NOT CHANGE THE EXPRESSION OF BLOOD EC MARKERS

Unless otherwise listed, CPT1a^{KD} refers to knockdown 1 (KD1) of the 2 non-overlapping shRNAs tested. **a**, Representative immunoblot for CPT1a and β -actin in LECs after silencing of CPT1a with two non-overlapping shRNAs (abbreviated as KD1 and KD2, respectively). **b**, Relative FAO flux in LECs at baseline and upon CPT1a^{KD} versus VECs (n = 3). **c**, Relative [³H]-thymidine incorporation in DNA in CPT1a^{KD} LECs (using KD2) versus control LECs (n = 3). The same control samples were used from Fig. 3a. **d**, Total sprout length in CPT1a^{KD} LEC spheroids (using KD2) versus control LEC spheroids (n = 3). The same control samples were used as Fig. 3c. **e**, Quantitation of the number of sprouts per spheroid in control LECs and upon CPT1a^{KD} (using KD1 or KD2) (n = 3). **f**, Measurement of lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) in the cell culture media as a measure of cell death in control and CPT1a^{KD} LECs (using KD1 or KD2) (n = 3). AU = arbitrary units. **g**, Relative FAO flux in pLECs at baseline and upon CPT1a^{KD} versus VECs (n = 3). **h-j**, Fold change in *ITGA9* (h), *CCL21* (i) and *PROX1* (j) mRNA expression in pLECs at baseline and upon CPT1a^{KD} versus VECs (n = 3). **k**, Fold change in *VEGFR3* mRNA expression in pLECs at baseline and after treatment with etomoxir versus VECs (n = 3). **l**, Fold change in *VLCAD* mRNA expression in pLECs at baseline and upon *VLCAD*^{KD} (n = 3). **m**, Relative FAO flux in LECs at baseline and upon *VLCAD*^{KD} (n = 3). **n**, Fold change in *VEGFR3* mRNA expression in pLECs at baseline and upon *VLCAD*^{KD} (n = 3). **o**, Relative FAO flux in VECs overexpressing CPT1a (CPT1a^{OE}) versus control-transduced VECs (ctrl) (n = 3). **p-r**, Fold change in *CPT1A* (p), *PROX1* (q) and *VEGFR3* (r) mRNA expression in CPT1a^{OE} VECs versus ctrl VECs (n = 3). **s-v**, Fold change in *CPT1A* (s), *KDR* (t), *EFNB2* (u) and *EPHB4* (v) mRNA expression in CPT1a^{KD} VECs versus ctrl VECs (n = 3). Mean \pm s.e.m. Statistical test: ANOVA and Bonferroni post-hoc test were used in multiple group comparisons. *t*-test was used for comparison of two groups. **p*<0.05, NS = not statistically significant.

EXTENDED DATA FIGURE 6: METABOLIC EFFECTS OF CPT1A^{KD} IN LECs

a-e, *In vitro* experiments with pLECs at baseline (ctrl) and with silencing of CPT1a (CPT1a^{KD}) versus VECs. **a**, Energy charge (n = 5). **b**, Percentage of oxidized glutathione (GSSG)/total glutathione (GSSG+GSH) (n = 3). **c**, Relative NADP⁺/NADPH ratio, expressed relative to ctrl VECs (n = 3). **d**, CM-H₂DCFDA (intracellular ROS) signal (n = 3). AU = arbitrary units. **e**, H₂O₂ levels, as detected with Amplex Red reagent (n = 3). *In vitro* experiments with CPT1a^{KD} pLECs versus ctrl pLECs. **f**, Percentage total contribution of [U-¹³C]-palmitate carbons to citrate (Cit), α -ketoglutarate (α KG), fumarate (Fum) and malate (Mal) (n = 3). **g**, Cellular pool size of citrate (Cit), α -ketoglutarate (α KG), fumarate (Fum) and malate (Mal), measured as arbitrary units (AU) of the metabolite of interest normalized to the protein content (n = 3). **h**, Relative incorporation of ¹⁴C-palmitate carbons into DNA (n = 3). **i**, Percentage total contribution of [U-¹³C]-palmitate carbons to aspartate (Asp), glutamate (Glu), UTP and CTP (n = 3). **j**, Cellular pool size of aspartate (Asp), glutamate (Glu), UTP, CTP, ATP and GTP, measured as arbitrary units (AU) of the metabolite of interest normalized to the protein content (n = 3). **k**, Total sprout length from spheroid sprouting assay in pLECs upon CPT1a^{KD}, without (ctrl) and with nucleotide (dNTP) supplementation versus pLECs without CPT1a^{KD} (ctrl). Note, the first two bars are the same data as Fig. 6e, performed in the same independent experiment (n = 3). Mean \pm s.e.m. of *n* independent experiments. Statistical test: ANOVA and Bonferroni post-hoc test were used in multiple group comparisons. *t*-test was used for comparison of two groups. **p*<0.05, NS = not statistically significant.

EXTENDED DATA FIGURE 7: ADDITIONAL DATA REGARDING PROX1-MEDIATED CPT1A UPREGULATION, THE EFFECT OF TARGETING p300 ON VEC-TO-LEC DIFFERENTIATION IN VITRO AND TARGETING SLC25A1 OR ACLY PHENOPIES CPT1A^{KD} IN INHIBITING VEC-TO-LEC DIFFERENTIATION IN VITRO

a, Fold change in *CPT1A* mRNA expression in VECs overexpressing native Prox1 (Prox1) or a DNA-binding Prox1 mutant (Prox1mut) *versus* control VECs (n = 3). **b**, Prox1 enrichment (using anti-Prox1 antibody) around the human *CPT1A* gene (green), as compared to input chromatin (black), as determined by ChIP-seq analysis of VECs transduced with a lentiviral vector expressing Prox1. Reads are binned in 100 bp intervals, and expressed per million reads (y axis). Displayed are averages of 2 independent ChIP-seq experiments. Top line: position of genes on chromosome 11; grey blocks denote *CPT1A* exons; black blocks denote exons of adjacent genes. Bottom line: chromosomal location (genome build hg19). The red arrowheads (A,B) above the chromosome location refers to statistically significant regions of Prox1 enrichment (q < 0.1; q-value is the FDR corrected p-value), corresponding to the regions identified in Fig. 3g. **c**, Quantitation of PCR of regions “A” and “B” from panel g for the *CPT1a* gene in Prox1 ChIP samples from VECs (empty-FLAG in Fig. 3g) and pLECs (Prox1-FLAG in Fig. 3g), expressed as percentage of input (n = 3). **d-f**, Fold change in *VEGFR3* (d), *ITGA9* (e) and *CCL21* (f) mRNA expression in pLECs treated with vehicle (ctrl) or p300 inhibitor SGC-CBP30 (SGC) *versus* VECs (n = 3). **g**, Fold change in *EP300* mRNA expression (gene encoding p300 protein) in pLECs with p300 silencing (p300^{KD}) *versus* pLECs with control silencing (ctrl) (n=3). **h-j**, Fold change in *VEGFR3* (h), *ITGA9* (i) and *CCL21* (j) mRNA expression in pLECs without (ctrl) and with p300 silencing *versus* VECs (n = 3). Note: as the level of p300 silencing was only approximately 50%, the degree of *VEGFR3*, *ITGA9* and *CCL21* reduction compared to control pLECs was less pronounced than treatment with the p300 inhibitor SGC-CBP30 (panels d-f). **k,l**, Fold change in *ITGA9* (k) and *CCL21* (l) mRNA expression in pLECs treated with vehicle (ctrl) or the SLC25A1 inhibitor 1,2,3-benzenetricarboxylate (BTC) *versus* VECs (n = 3). **m,n**, Fold change in *ITGA9* (m) and *CCL21* (n) mRNA expression in pLECs without (ctrl) and with ATP-citrate lyase (ACLY)

silencing (ACLY^{KD}; lowering *ACLY* mRNA levels by $\pm 75\%$) versus VECs (n = 3). **o-q**, Fold change in *ACLY* (o), *CPT1A* (p) and *VEGFR3* (q) mRNA expression in pLECs at baseline (ctrl) and upon silencing of ACLY (ACLY^{KD}) (n = 5). **r**, Relative FAO flux in pLECs at baseline (ctrl) and upon silencing of ACLY (ACLY^{KD}) (n = 4). **s**, Intracellular pools of malonyl-CoA determined by LC-MS in pLECs at baseline (ctrl) and upon silencing of ACLY (ACLY^{KD}), expressed as relative malonyl-CoA : acetyl-CoA : CoA ratios (n = 3). Mean \pm s.e.m. of *n* independent experiments. Statistical test: ANOVA and Bonferroni post-hoc test were used in multiple group comparisons. *t*-test was used for comparison of two groups. Statistical analysis for CHIP-seq described in Methods. **p*<0.05, NS = not statistically significant.

EXTENDED DATA FIGURE 8: DYNAMIC REGULATION OF H3K9AC AT LEC GENES, AND PROX1 DOES NOT INTERACT WITH THE KDR GENE OR AFFECT H3K9 ACETYLATION AT THE KDR GENE

a, Proportion of LEC *versus* non-LEC genes (refers to all annotated genes not included in LEC ontology) with enhanced H3K9ac (red portion) in pLECs *versus* VECs. The green portion denotes genes without significantly enhanced H3K9ac levels. **b**, Proportion of Prox1-target genes *versus* unrelated genes with enhanced H3K9ac (red portion) in pLECs *versus* VECs. The green portion denotes genes without significantly enhanced H3K9ac levels. **c-f**, H3K9ac enrichment around the *PROX1* (c) and *SOX18* (e) genes in VECs (blue) and pLECs without (green) and with CPT1a^{KD} (dark blue). Top line above each snapshot: scheme of the gene; grey blocks denote the exons of the gene of interest; black blocks denote exons of adjacent genes. Red arrowheads indicate sites of Prox1 enrichment in the *PROX1* (c) or *SOX18* (e) genes. Bottom line under each snapshot: chromosomal location of the gene (human genome build GRCh37/hg19). Grey boxes at the chromosomal locations denote regions with H3K9ac peak areas as determined using MACS. When the top half of the box is green, it denotes regions of significantly enhanced H3K9ac in pLECs *versus* VECs. When the bottom half of the box is red, it denotes regions of significantly reduced H3K9ac in pLECs with CPT1a^{KD} *versus* pLECs. q-value is the FDR corrected p-value. Quantitative PCR verification of H3K9ac ChIP-seq results for the sequences of *PROX1* (d) and *SOX18* (f) (asterisks in panels c and e, respectively) on H3K9ac ChIP samples from pLECs without (ctrl) and with CPT1a silencing (CPT1a^{KD}) *versus* VECs, expressed as relative to input (n = 3). **g**, p300 enrichment around the *VEGFR3* gene in VECs (blue) and pLECs (green). Top line: scheme of the gene; grey blocks denote the exons of the gene of interest; black blocks denote exons of adjacent genes. Red arrowheads indicate Prox1 binding sites. Bottom line: chromosomal location of the gene (human genome build GRCh37/hg19); grey boxes at the chromosomal locations: regions with H3K9ac peak areas. Asterisk denotes region confirmed by qPCR in panel h. **h**, Quantitative PCR verification of p300 ChIP-seq results for the sequence of *VEGFR3* on p300 ChIP samples from pLECs *versus* VECs as a percentage of input, expressed as relative to VEC. **i**, Prox1-FLAG enrichment around the human *KDR*

(VEGFR2) gene (Prox1-FLAG, green) *versus* empty-FLAG control (empty-FLAG, blue) in VECs transduced with a lentiviral vector expressing FLAG-tagged Prox1 (Prox1-FLAG) or empty-FLAG, and Prox1 enrichment (using anti-Prox1 antibody ChIP) in pLECs (Prox1, green) and VECs (GFP, blue), as compared to the input chromatin (purple) and determined by ChIP-seq analysis. Top line: scheme of the *KDR* gene; grey blocks denote *KDR* exons and black blocks denote exons of adjacent genes. Bottom line: chromosomal location (human genome build GRCh37/hg19) ($q < 0.1$; q-value is the FDR corrected p-value. **j**, H3K9ac enrichment around the human *KDR* gene in VECs (blue) and pLECs (green). Top line: scheme of the *KDR* gene; grey blocks denote *KDR* exons and black blocks denote exons of adjacent genes. Bottom line: chromosomal location (human genome build GRCh37/hg19). q-value is the FDR corrected p-value. Mean \pm s.e.m. of n independent experiments. Statistical test: Chi-square test was used to compare gene ontology subsets for presence of increased H3K9ac. ANOVA and Bonferroni post-hoc test were used in multiple group comparisons. Statistical analysis for ChIP-seq is described in Methods. * $p < 0.05$.

EXTENDED DATA FIGURE 9: PROX1 OVEREXPRESSION INCREASES P300 BINDING AND H3K9 ACETYLATION AT THE CPT1A GENE

a, p300 enrichment around the human *CPT1A* gene in VECs (blue) and pLECs (green), as determined by CHIP-seq analysis of VECs transduced with a lentiviral vector expressing a control vector (GFP) or Prox1, respectively. Reads are binned as 100 bp intervals, and expressed per million reads (y axis). Displayed are averages of 2 independent CHIP-seq experiments. Top line: scheme of the *CPT1a* gene; grey blocks denote CPT1A exons and black blocks denote exons of adjacent genes. Bottom line: chromosomal location (human genome build GRCh37/hg19). The red arrowheads (A,B) above the chromosome location refer to statistically significant regions of Prox1 enrichment from Fig. 3g. **b,c**, p300 ChIP and qPCR for the Prox1 binding site at *CPT1A-A* (b) or *CPT1A-B* (c) in pLECs without (ctrl) and with CPT1a silencing (*CPT1a*^{KD}) versus VECs, values expressed as a percentage of input and relative to VECs (n = 3). **d**, H3K9ac enrichment around the human *CPT1A* gene in VECs (blue) and pLECs (green), as determined by CHIP-seq analysis of VECs transduced with a lentiviral vector expressing a control vector (GFP) or Prox1, respectively. Top line: scheme of the *CPT1a* gene; grey blocks denote CPT1A exons and black blocks denote exons of adjacent genes. Bottom line: chromosomal location (genome build hg19). The red arrowheads (A,B) above the chromosome location refer to statistically significant regions of Prox1 enrichment from Fig. 3g. q-value is the FDR corrected p-value. **e**, Quantitative PCR of the Prox1-binding regions “A” and “B” of the *CPT1A* gene (illustrated in panel d) on H3K9ac ChIP samples from pLECs versus VECs, calculated as relative to the input and expressed relative to the values obtained for VECs (n = 3). **f,g**, Quantitation of the densitometry from Prox1 ChIP and PCR for the Prox1 binding site at *CPT1A-A* (f) or *CPT1A-B* (g) (identified in Fig. 3g) in pLECs without (ctrl) and with CPT1a silencing (*CPT1a*^{KD}) versus VECs, expressed as relative to input (n = 3). **h**, Quantitation of the densitometry from Prox1 ChIP and PCR for the Prox1 binding site at *VEGFR3* in pLECs without (ctrl) and with CPT1a silencing (*CPT1a*^{KD}) versus VECs, expressed as relative to input (n = 3). **i**, p300 ChIP and qPCR for the Prox1 binding site at *VEGFR3* in pLECs without (ctrl) and with CPT1a silencing (*CPT1a*^{KD}) versus VECs, values

expressed as a percentage of input and relative to VECs ($n = 3$). Mean \pm s.e.m. of n independent experiments. Statistical test: ANOVA and Bonferroni post-hoc test were used in multiple group comparisons. t -test was used for comparison of two groups. * $p < 0.05$, NS = not statistically significant.

EXTENDED DATA FIGURE 10: PHARMACOLOGICAL INHIBITION OF FAO RESULTS IN DEFECTS IN ANGIOGENESIS

a,b, Quantitation of lymphatic vessel end-point density (number of vessel extremities per corneal area; a) and lymphatic vessel length density (cumulative length of the lymphatic vessel network; b), both parameters per total corneal area, in WT mice subjected to corneal cauterization-induced injury treated daily with vehicle (ctrl) or etomoxir in Fig. 5e-k (n = 5 animals per group). **c**, Representative images of CD31⁺ blood vessel outgrowth 9 days after corneal cauterization-induced injury in adult WT mice treated daily with vehicle (ctrl) or etomoxir. Scale bars: 250 μ m. **d-g**, Quantitation of percentage blood vessel outgrowth area relative to total area (d), branch point density (e), end-point density (f) and length density (g) in WT mice subjected to corneal cauterization-induced injury treated daily with vehicle (ctrl) or etomoxir from the corneal cauterization experiments in Fig. 5e-k (n = 5 animals per group). **h**, Measurement of plasma acetate concentrations in mice treated with PBS (ctrl) or 400 μ L of 0.5 M acetate (ac) for 9 days (n = 6 mice per group). **i,j**, Quantitation of lymphatic vessel end-point density (number of vessel extremities per corneal area; i) and lymphatic vessel length density (cumulative length of the lymphatic vessel network) (j), both parameters per total corneal area, in WT mice subjected to corneal cauterization-induced injury treated daily with vehicle (ctrl), acetate only (ac), etomoxir only (eto) or etomoxir plus acetate (eto+ac) from the corneal cauterization experiments in Fig. 6f-j (n = 10 animals per group). **k**, Traditional and adapted model of the mechanism of Prox1-induced lymphatic formation. Traditional model: Prox1 binds to the promoter region of lymphangiogenic genes, including VEGFR3, enhancing their transcription. Adapted model: By binding to the CPT1a promoter, Prox1 induces CPT1a expression, enhancing the production of FAO-derived acetyl-CoA. In a dual manner, FAO (red) thereby regulates: (i) LEC proliferation via providing acetyl-CoA, which helps to sustain the TCA cycle and deoxyribonucleotide (dNTP) synthesis in conjunction with an anaplerotic substrate during lymphangiogenesis (purple); and (ii) lymphangiogenic gene expression via supplying acetyl-CoA used for histone acetylation (Ac) at lymphangiogenic genes,

thereby modulating LEC differentiation, proliferation and migration (green). Prox1 promotes histone acetylation preferentially at lymphatic genes by enriching p300 at Prox1-binding sites, and by supplying more acetyl-CoA (through FAO induction). Thus, in the adapted model, Prox1 still functions as a *bona fide* transcription factor (as proposed in the traditional model), but its role is extended by utilizing FAO metabolism to enhance its own transcriptional activity. Mean \pm s.e.m.; (n = 5 animals per group from 1 experiment in a,b,d-g), (n = 6 animals per group from 1 experiment in h), (n = 6 animals per group from 2 experiments in i,j). Statistical test: ANOVA and Bonferroni post-hoc test were used in multiple group comparisons. *t*-test was used for comparison of two groups. * $p < 0.05$.

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE LEGEND

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE: Uncropped scans with size marker indication for Fig. 1d, Fig. 3e, Fig. 3i, Fig. 4d, Fig. 6b, Fig. 6c and Extended Data Fig. 5a.

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLE 1: PEAKS FROM PROX1-FLAG CHIP-SEQ AND MAPPING OF PROX1, H3K9AC AND P300 CHIP-SEQ DATA.

5,611 peaks were called using MACS analysis on Prox1-FLAG ChIP-seq data. Similarly listed are reads mapping to PROX1-FLAG peak areas upon ChIP-seq for Prox1 (Prox1 recognized by the anti-Prox1 antibody), H3K9ac and p300, and upon sequencing the Prox1-ChIP input sample (values listed in reads per million). Peak coordinates are according to human genome assembly GRCh37/hg19.

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLE 2: PEAKS FROM H3K9AC CHIP-SEQ IN PLECS VERSUS VECs AND PLECS UPON CPT1A^{KD} VERSUS PLECS AT BASELINE.

41,241 H3K9ac peaks were called using MACS analysis in VECs and pLECs at baseline and upon CPT1a^{KD}. Changes in H3K9ac signal at peak areas in pLECs *versus* VECs or pLECs upon CPT1a^{KD} *versus* pLECs at baseline were called using EdgeR software. Peak coordinates are according to human genome assembly GRCh37/hg19.

SUPPLEMENTARY DISCUSSION

In the supplementary discussion, we provide additional rationale, description and discussion of experiments, which we could not include into the main text due to space restrictions. These data are shown in the Extended Data Figures.

SUPPLEMENTARY DISCUSSION 1 – *Residual CPT1a protein precludes analysis of early lymphatic development*

We could not study the role of complete loss of CPT1a in early lymphatic development, because of the following reasons: (i) use of the *Prox1-Cre^{ERT2}*, *Prox1^{FK}-Cre* and *Flt4-Cre^{ERT2}* lines all possess the inevitable limitation that *CPT1a* becomes inactivated only after Prox1 initiates lymphatic development and not all CPT1a protein is immediately and sufficiently rapidly cleared in LEC precursors and LECs (Extended Data Fig. 2f-j), despite detection of a CPT1a excision band as early as E9.5 (Extended Data Fig. 2k), thereby still allowing residual lymphatic formation at E14.5 (data not shown); and (ii) CPT1a protein stability precluded rapid clearance of CPT1a; even despite a very efficient lowering of CPT1a mRNA levels (Extended Data Fig. 2l), CPT1a protein levels remained much higher, resulting in 35-40% residual CPT1a protein levels 3 days after CPT1a silencing (Extended Data Fig. 2m).

We considered using *VE-cadherin(PAC)-Cre^{ERT2}* mice (also known as *Cdh5(PAC)-Cre^{ERT2}*), as they express Cre^{ERT2} in VECs of the cardinal vein prior to LEC precursor specification³⁷ in order to obtain earlier CPT1a excision, but these mice exhibited blood vascular defects (as expected, based on our previously characterized role of CPT1a in blood vascular endothelial cells (BECs)¹¹), which precluded us from studying lymphatic development (Extended Data Fig. 2n).

SUPPLEMENTARY DISCUSSION 2 – **VLCAD SILENCING PHENOCOPIES CPT1A SILENCING AND CPT1A OVEREXPRESSION IS NOT SUFFICIENT TO INDUCE VEC-TO-LEC DIFFERENTIATION**

Silencing of very long chain acyl-CoA dehydrogenase (VLCAD^{KD}), a gene directly involved in the FAO pathway, phenocopied the effects of CPT1a^{KD} in pLECs, reducing FAO flux and *VEGFR3* mRNA expression (Extended Data Fig. 5l-n). However, CPT1a overexpression in VECs increased the FAO flux, but was unable to induce VEC-to-LEC differentiation (Extended Data Fig. 5o-r), implying that FAO is essential but not sufficient for the Prox1-mediated induction of LEC differentiation, and may require the coordinated activity of Prox1. In line, CPT1a^{KD} in VECs did not impair the expression of blood vascular EC (BEC) markers (*KDR*, *EFNB2*, *EPHB4*) (Extended Data Fig. 5s-v). These data also suggest that FAO is downstream of Prox1.

SUPPLEMENTARY DISCUSSION 3 – ADDITIONAL METABOLIC PARAMETERS OF FAO IN LECs

FAO regulates mediators of redox homeostasis

CPT1a^{KD} trended to slightly elevate oxidized glutathione levels (GSSG levels, percent of the total glutathione (GSSG+GSH) levels), although this increase was not statistically significant. The NADP⁺ / NADPH ratio was also elevated upon CPT1a^{KD} in pLECs, but did not cause significant changes in reactive oxygen species levels in pLECs (Extended Data Fig. 6b,c). As we also observed no differences in cellular ROS or H₂O₂ levels (Extended Data Fig. 6d,e), we speculate that the reduction in ROS scavenging capacity is balanced by a reduction in ROS generation upon CPT1a^{KD}.

FAO-derived acetyl-CoA contributes to TCA intermediates and nucleotide precursors necessary for nucleotide synthesis

We recently documented another metabolic role of FAO in VECs, namely that FAO regulates proliferation of these BECs by generating fatty acid-derived carbons for incorporation into deoxyribonucleotide during DNA replication ¹¹. Stable isotopomer analysis with [U-¹³C]-palmitate revealed that CPT1a^{KD} in pLECs reduced the incorporation of labeled carbons in TCA cycle metabolites (citrate, α -ketoglutarate, fumarate, malate; Extended Data Fig. 6f) and reduced total pools of these metabolites

(Extended Data Fig. 6g), phenocopying VECs¹¹. This mechanism also regulated, at least in part, the proliferation of LECs, since CPT1a^{KD} reduced ¹⁴C-palmitate incorporation into DNA in LECs (Extended Data Fig. 6h), similar as in VECs¹¹. Use of [U-¹³C]-palmitate further revealed that CPT1a^{KD} in pLECs decreased tracer incorporation into the nucleotide precursors aspartate, glutamate, UTP and CTP (Extended Data Fig. 6i), and also resulted in a reduction in the total pools of aspartate, glutamate, UTP, CTP, ATP and GTP (Extended Data Fig. 6j). Further, supplementation of a nucleotide mix to CPT1a^{KD} pLEC spheroids completely rescued sprouting to baseline levels (Extended Data Fig. 6k). These results show that LECs, like BECs, use FAO to generate carbons for incorporation into dNTPs during DNA synthesis.

SUPPLEMENTARY DISCUSSION 4 – CHARACTERIZATION OF THE ACLY^{KD} PHENOTYPE AND STATEMENT ON HISTONE DEACETYLATION

We assessed whether the phenocopy of the CPT1a^{KD} phenotype by ACLY^{KD} was due to reduced CPT1a expression in pLECs. ACLY^{KD} lowered *CPT1A* mRNA expression (Extended Data Fig. 7o,p) and decreased *VEGFR3* mRNA expression (Extended Data Fig. 7q), however, without significantly altering FAO flux (Extended Data Fig. 7r), likely due to decreased pools of malonyl-CoA, an inhibitor of FAO (Extended Data Fig. 7s).

Histone acetylation can also be inversely regulated by histone deacetylases. For instance, butyrate, a fatty acid metabolite produced by colonic bacteria, increases histone acetylation either by inhibiting histone deacetylation through inhibition of histone deacetylases (HDACs) or by providing acetyl-CoA through FAO⁴³. We did not specifically focus on the role of HDACs in the regulation of lymphangiogenesis, as we discovered a novel interaction between Prox1 and p300, and Prox1-mediated FAO-driven acetyl-CoA production promotes the expression of lymph-angiogenic genes. Whether histone deacetylation also regulates lymphangiogenesis in this context merits further study.

SUPPLEMENTARY REFERENCES

- 43 Donohoe, D. R. *et al.* The Warburg effect dictates the mechanism of butyrate-mediated histone acetylation and cell proliferation. *Mol Cell* **48**, 612-626 (2012).